

FAIR Vocabularies and Authority Files for Museums and Collections

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Abstract

Controlled vocabularies and authority data are central to the reusability of data used to describe objects in museums and collections. The [Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections](#) already contains key guidance on terminology use in core elements of object documentation.

This report presents a series of relevant vocabularies for collection documentation, including those suitable for specific documentation focuses and disciplines. Each one is assessed according to the criteria of the internationally recognised [FAIR Principles](#), and a brief description is provided of the respective content focuses and the technical implementation status of the web offerings. This allows museum and collection professionals, as well as those who reuse datasets, to make an informed assessment of the sustainability of the described vocabularies in the context of linked publishing and effective research data management.

This paper was prepared by a sub-working group of the [Minimum Record Working Group](#) of the Fachgruppe Dokumentation of the German Museum Association (DMB). The group comprises staff and representatives from the German Digital Library, the Humboldt-Universität Berlin (Coordination Centre for Scientific University Collections in Germany), the Institute for Museum Research, the Klassik Stiftung Weimar, the Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich, Philipps-Universität Marburg (Deutsches Dokumentationszentrum für Kunstgeschichte - Bildarchiv Foto Marburg), and the Verbundzentrale des Gemeinsamen Bibliotheksverbunds Göttingen (VZG).

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1. Introduction

The use of controlled vocabularies for documenting digital objects in museums and collections has long been recommended and is becoming increasingly widespread¹. It enables technically appropriate and consistent keyword descriptions of objects and supports the discoverability of collection data in cross-application contexts. Examples include cultural heritage portals such as Europeana and the German Digital Library, as well as knowledge graphs such as those of [NFDI4Culture](#) and [NFDI4Objects](#).

'Controlled vocabulary' is an umbrella term for documentation languages created according to defined rules to enable the identification, differentiation, and classification of concepts². A concept is a 'an idea or notion; a unit of thought'³ to which various linguistic designations, definitions and other attributes can be assigned.

Concepts relating to historical entities, such as individuals, organisations, places, works, objects or events, are relevant for collection documentation. These concepts are identified and described using authority data. Generic concepts, on the other hand, are used to provide information on the type and classification of objects, as well as their subject, materials and techniques. A generic concept refers to a characteristic common to several objects, grouping them into classes. The characteristics can be very specific or very broad. For this reason, generic concepts in controlled vocabularies are often organised into hierarchies of superordinate and subordinate concepts. An example is 'hay cart' – 'cart' (agriculture) – 'farm vehicle' (agriculture) – 'agricultural implement'. This group includes thesauri, classifications, typologies, systems and taxonomies.

Data on collection holdings is also highly relevant for research purposes. Object descriptions are based on research and scientific verification. This ensures that other researchers can find the data and provides the essential historical context. To be as useful as possible in increasingly international, interconnected analysis scenarios, which are equally determined by humans and algorithms, data describing collections should comply with the FAIR Principles⁴ wherever possible.

¹ Rahemipour, P., Grotz, K. (eds., 2023). Statistische Gesamterhebung an den Museen der Bundesrepublik Deutschland 2021. Zahlen und Materialien aus dem Institut für Museumsforschung, Heft 77. Institut für Museumsforschung - Staatliche Museen zu Berlin, Tab.47b, <https://doi.org/10.11588/ifmzm.2023.1>

Schlösser, M., Schäfer, J., von Hagel, F., Schäfer, F. (2025). Überblick über das Forschungsdatenmanagement in Museen und Universitäts-sammlungen. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14926511> and presentation with detailed results <https://cloud.nfdi4culture.de/s/6ccmp9wxiNSEXJ4>

² Sandrock, J., Lindenthal, J. (2023). digiCULT Thesaurus-Handbuch. <https://digiicult.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/XTREE/pages/3305177117/Thesaurus-Handbuch>
Moeller, K., Purschwitz, A. (2025). Kontrollierte Vokabulare und Normdaten der historisch arbeitenden Disziplinen (1.0). Historisches Datenzentrum Sachsen-Anhalt. p. 3, 9ff. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15745568>

³ Miles, A., Bechhofer, S. (ed.). SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference. W3C Recommendation 18 August 2009. (2009). 3.1 Preamble. <https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference>

⁴ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for Scientific Data Management and Stewardship. Scientific Data 3:160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
Kailus, A. (2025). Guideline for a FAIR Management of Cultural Research Data (2.0.1) [Dataset]. NFDI4Culture. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17055222>

Since their publication in 2016, the FAIR principles have become an internationally recognised model for managing research data. These fifteen general recommendations aim to make data as findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable as possible. The use of terminology plays a key role in this. It ensures the semantic interoperability of data in technical and scientific contexts through the use of Linked Open Data⁵. To fully exploit the potential of object-related data on the Semantic Web, therefore, vocabularies must be as machine-readable, open, and interoperable as possible.

However, it is often unclear what specifically characterises FAIR vocabulary, or how 'FAIR' certain vocabularies are. To make their valuable data collections available in the most sustainable way possible, museums and collections must choose vocabulary that is not only professionally appropriate, but also supports the FAIR provision and reuse of data.

This publication by the Minimum Record Working Group offers guidance on the subject. It provides a systematic overview of selected relevant vocabularies for museums and collections. It thus serves as a supplement to the Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections (MDS)⁶. Since the MDS had to be concise, it only recommends the most important and well-known vocabularies for the respective data elements. This publication goes beyond this by also including additional vocabularies suitable for specific object types, documentation focuses, and disciplines, as well as by assessing the FAIRness of the offerings. This closes the gaps that had to be deliberately left open in the MDS.

The selection of vocabularies is based on their relevance to museums and collections, and on their familiarity and actual use within this community. Important networks and cultural heritage portals in Germany are also taken into account. However, it does not list all possible vocabularies. Apart from the suitability of the content for the respective documentation tasks, museum and collection staff can use the published FAIR classification criteria to assess the reusability of other vocabularies themselves. Another prerequisite for inclusion in this compilation is digital publication of the vocabulary.

The focus is on table-based lists of vocabulary and properties that group together content-related and technical information. These are supplemented by indicators for assessing the FAIR level. The assessment is based on current research⁷ defining criteria for the FAIRness of vocabularies. This helps museums and collections to make informed decisions about using suitable vocabularies, developing their data to a higher standard and

⁵ Berners-Lee, T. (2006). Linked Data - Design Issues.

<http://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

⁶ Minimum Record Working Group, Marchini, C., Ando, M., Böhm, E., Bernhard, A.-M., Diepenbrock, N., Frech, A., Götsch, S., Gerber, A., Gnyp, A., Greisinger, S., Grotrian, E., von Hagel, F., Kailus, A., Koch, A.-M., Kudlinski, V., Nowicki, A.-L., Purschwitz, A., Quade, L., ... Wassermann, S. (2025). Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections (MDS v1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17314095>

⁷ Xu, F., Juty, N., Goble, C. et al. (2023). Features of a FAIR vocabulary. *Journal of Biomedical Semantics* 14:6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-023-00286-8>

Hugo, W., Le Franc, Y., Coen, G., Parland-von Essen, J., Bonino, L. (2020). D2.5 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Second Iteration (1.0). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5362010>

Cox, S. J. D., Gonzalez-Beltran, A. N., Magagna, B., Marinescu, M.-C. (2021). Ten simple rules for making a vocabulary FAIR. *PLoS Computational Biology* 17(6): e1009041.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009041>

RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group. (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model. Specification and Guidelines. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

publishing it in a FAIR manner. Secondly, the article aims to raise awareness within the professional community of the strategic importance of vocabularies for linked open data and digital research infrastructures.

2. Criteria for assessing the FAIRness of vocabularies

The evaluation uses a traffic light system to provide a quick overview. If a vocabulary is rated yellow or red, the reasons for the rating are provided.

The assessment is based on the currently published status of vocabulary services and other published sources (whether digital or analogue) to ensure transparency for users. However, information obtained through direct communication with editorial boards or service providers regarding future features that have not yet been implemented is not taken into account.

The preconditions for evaluation according to certain FAIR criteria can change quickly, particularly following a service's technical development. The evaluation presented here represents a snapshot taken in autumn 2025 (editorial deadline: 30 November 2025). To keep users informed about the implementation status and further development of the services, this publication will be updated regularly.

If a vocabulary is available from several providers, the FAIR rating may vary according to provider, as the characteristics of the services usually differ. Some vocabularies have supplementary services that offer human users different search options or result presentations. However, their content is approximately as up to date as that of the main service, and they refer to the main provider's data retrieval services (e.g. Online-GND, GND-Explorer, AAT-Deutsch). These services were not considered separately in the FAIR classification as they do not aim to provide the full range of functions.

Mapping services such as Cocoda, as well as reconciliation APIs (services specifically tailored to data matching and enrichment), also integrate a number of the vocabularies listed here. While they are included because of their relevance to museums and collections, they are not considered in the FAIR classification due to their specific application purpose.

It is possible to differentiate a single vocabulary resource if distinct parts of the vocabulary differ significantly in terms of certain FAIRness criteria. If one serialisation of a resource meets a FAIR criterion and another does not, the component with the highest level of FAIRness is evaluated.

The FAIRness of the vocabulary offerings must be assessed with regard to the human- and machine-readable file formats provided. Open formats, such as XML, JSON and CSV, allow the semantic structure of the data to be represented and can therefore be processed directly. In contrast, HTML and PDF are considered unstructured formats. Therefore, even if it is possible to obtain structured information by further processing such data, they are classified as human-readable only.

The following section explains the individual FAIR criteria and presents the criteria used to classify the respective vocabularies.

2.1 The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1)

A PID (Persistent Identifier) is a permanent reference that uniquely identifies an entity, such as a vocabulary, concept, place, object, person or institution. To facilitate its use in digital, linked applications, the PID must be accessible via a stable web address that ensures consistent access to the associated content (URI, IRI).

Green: The vocabulary itself is available via a persistent URL. This may also be the URL of the vocabulary's root node. Persistence is assumed if the vocabulary has been available at this address for some time, with no indication that the service will be discontinued in the future.

Examples:

- <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/> for Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus
- <https://term.museum-digital.de/moebel/tag/1> for the root element of Furniture Classification (Möbeltypologie) at museum-digital

Yellow: The vocabulary itself cannot be addressed directly via a persistent URL. However, it has a URI at Wikidata or in a registry (a catalogue of relevant services with associated metadata, e.g. BARTOC). The vocabulary can be addressed indirectly via the URL listed there.

Red: The vocabulary itself is not available directly via a persistent URL, nor does it have a URI at Wikidata or in a registry.

2.2 Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1)

Green: A persistent identifier is provided for each concept. This identifier is displayed in human-readable representations and included in machine-readable serialisation as a web link, marked as a concept identifier.

Yellow: An identifier is provided for each concept, but it is only human-readable (there is no URI; it is only provided on the website or in a PDF).

The identifier is unlikely to meet the criterion of global uniqueness.

Serialisations do not contain the PID in the form of a web link. The PID cannot be supplemented with a base URL (the part of a website address that remains unchanged) and access to the resource is not possible even after supplementation.

Red: Concepts have no human- or machine-readable identifiers.

2.3 It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4)

The search should be possible for both humans and machines. Application programming interfaces (APIs) or other interfaces enable machine access for tasks such as obtaining or integrating data into another application. Special reconciliation APIs allow local datasets to be compared with tools such as OpenRefine and mapped to specific vocabularies.

Green: Both humans and machines can search for the vocabulary itself, which leads to the PID of the vocabulary.

Humans can search for a term on a website or in a file, and the results display contains the identifier of the concept. Machines can also search via at least one interface/API, and the results contain the respective PID of the concept.

Yellow: Searching for terms is only possible for humans. Either there is no interface available, or the interface is not published, or access to it is restricted. However, there is a download option for structured data formats (XML, JSON, and CSV), which can be searched using additional software.

Red: Searching is only possible for humans. There is no interface or download option for structured file formats.

Searching is not possible for humans or machines. The vocabulary is only available in printed books or manuscripts, not as a file.

The only download option is for unstructured data formats (e.g. PDF), which must first be processed for machine use.

No identifiers in the form of URIs are offered for the vocabulary or concepts.

2.4 The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3)

In this context, a repository is a service that stores metadata relating to a vocabulary, as well as its content and versions. It also provides access to these resources. If the appropriate interfaces are available, both humans and machines can search for and find individual concepts, including their metadata, and reuse them. A repository is considered to be recognised by the community if it is known there and considered trustworthy in terms of its content and operators. Examples: GND at DNB or Lobid; the Getty websites for their vocabularies; and DANTE of the VZG.

Green: In this case, the repository is the vocabulary website itself. The provider is considered trustworthy and recognised by the community as an expert, as is the case for all services examined here.

2.5 When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4)

Dereferencing means that the addressed resource can be accessed via the identifier concept (PID), i.e. the web link is resolved. 'Representation' refers to the specific digital formats in which the data is serialised, e.g., [RDF XML](#) with [SKOS](#) or [OWL](#), [RDF Turtle](#), [RDF N-Triples](#), [RDF TriG](#) and [JSON-LD](#).

Serialisation involves transferring a data structure into a specific, storable, sequential format. The same structured information is often offered in different serialisations (for example, Getty AAT is provided as JSON, RDF, N3/Turtle, N-Triples or HTML).

Different human- or machine-readable formats can be addressed by modifying the URI.
Examples:

AAT: panel paintings:

<http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300033656> (human-readable) or
<https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033656.json>, <https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033656.rdf>,
<https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033656.ttl>, <https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033656.nt>
(maschine-readable)

This FAIR criterion is primarily relevant when it comes to dereferencing concepts.

Green: The identifier for a concept can return either a human-readable form, such as an HTML page or a PDF, or a machine-readable serialisation, such as JSON or RDF. For this purpose, two syntactic forms of the URI are usually created, both of which refer to the same numerical identifier. Both forms are possible.

Examples:

- museum-digital: <https://term.museum-digital.de/moebel/tag/329> (HTML) and <https://term.museum-digital.de/moebel/tag/329/json>
- AAT: <http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300038151> (HTML) and <https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300038151.json>

Yellow: The service only provides one form of representation, which the URI dereferences. This is usually in a human-readable format, such as HTML or PDF. This can also be implemented at the vocabulary level. The PID points to a PDF containing the entire vocabulary. Either there is no interface service, or it is not published, or access to it is restricted.

Red: Dereferencing via a web-enabled identifier is not possible at either the vocabulary or concept level. This would be conceivable in the case of a vocabulary that is only available on an analogue medium, for example. Whether the analogue work has an identifier (e.g. in WorldCat) is irrelevant here, as the vocabulary cannot be accessed using digital methods.

2.6 The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3)

If the service can be found under the name of the vocabulary in a web browser, it is discoverable by search engines. The 'searchable resource' may be the website itself, the terminology of which can be searched by humans or via machine interfaces. However, the vocabularies themselves can also be found on Wikidata or via a registry. Other searchable resources include terminology services (e.g. DANTE) and discovery systems (library reference systems based on search engine technology).

Green: Terms in the vocabulary can be searched for individually via the search interface of the web offering or in discovery systems and/or terminology services, and can also be accessed via interfaces/APIs.

Optional: The vocabulary is listed in either a registry or on Wikidata. If this is not the case, it does not lead to a downgrade.

Yellow: The vocabulary itself can be found directly via Wikidata or a registry. However, the terms are not indexed individually. For example, only a file containing the entire vocabulary is available to download, or the vocabulary is only available in analogue form.

Red: Neither the vocabulary itself nor the terms are registered or indexed on the web.

2.7 The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2)

This criterion refers to the communication protocols used to transfer data between servers and clients within the network. Data should be retrievable, particularly using identifiers, without the need for special or proprietary tools or communication methods. HTTP(S) and FTP protocols are widely used here.

The question of whether the protocol supports authentication and authorisation is only relevant if vocabularies are to be accessible to certain groups of people or for certain usage scenarios.

Green: The vocabulary and its concepts are accessible via HTTP(S). Even if individual concepts or terms cannot be searched for or addressed directly via their PIDs, this is still the case if the file containing them is accessible via a standardised protocol. This applies to all of the services reviewed here.

2.8 Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2)

Permanent availability is assumed unless there is information to the contrary. Contraindicators could include explicit indications from the provider or the creation of the vocabulary within a time-limited project, where there is no guarantee of further hosting by an institution or inclusion in a research data repository (digital long-term archive).

Concepts: If a duplicate concept record that has already been published is withdrawn during a subsequent duplicate check, a redirect service must be set up to the URI of the remaining concept record. This also dereferences the PID of the withdrawn record.

Green: The resource is expected to be permanently available. A redirect service exists.

Yellow: There are clear signs that the resource may not be permanently available. A redirect service does not exist, is not documented, or is clearly malfunctioning.

Red: The resource is demonstrably and foreseeably not permanently available. A redirect service does not exist.

2.9 The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2)

Versioning means that changes to data are logged and previous versions can be restored. When it comes to research data, it is good practice to give users access to all published versions, including older ones. With regard to vocabularies and their concepts, this means that each previous version can be permanently identified and retrieved. This is not the case for any of the examined vocabularies. However, since the meaning of a concept must not be changed when a data record is revised, this does not result in a downgrade. In terms of consistency, the criterion of the redirect service (see the previous FAIR criterion) is more important than accessibility of previous full versions of data records.

Versioning for vocabularies is typically indicated at the level of concept records through elements such as the creation date (`dateCreated`) and the modification date (`dateModified`). Sometimes, a modification history is also available which describes the nature of the modifications made. However, modifications are often not documented. While the creation date of the data record is sometimes specified, it is of secondary importance for managing different versions. If a vocabulary is available in several places, the instances will usually have different update statuses compared to the main editorially maintained instance (GND being the exception). Users need to be able to assess whether a more up-to-date and comprehensive version of the vocabulary is available elsewhere.

For the FAIRness assessment, we check whether this information is available in human-readable form only on the website or in a PDF file, or whether it is also included in the machine-readable serialisations of the data.

Green: The date on which the concept record was last modified is included in the web display and in at least one machine-readable serialisation. The creation date, modification history, or full availability of earlier versions of the record may also be provided.

Yellow: The date of the last modification of the concept record is only included in the web display or PDF, and not in at least one machine-readable serialisation. Alternatively, it is not included in human-readable formats but is included in at least one machine-readable serialisation.

It is likely that the offer has not been updated since it was made available, and the creation date is included in the web display and at least one machine-readable serialisation.

Red: The creation and last modification dates of the concept record are not included in the web display or at least one serialisation. This makes it unclear whether the offer has been updated since it was made available.

2.10 The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1)

The decisive factor for this criterion is whether the machine-readable serialisations [RDF XML](#) with [SKOS](#) or [OWL](#), [JSON-LD](#), and [JSKOS](#) which are particularly suitable in the context of the Semantic Web, are offered. With the exception of the relatively recently developed JSKOS, these are [W3C](#) recommendations, an organisation that supports the standardisation of web technologies.

Unlike JSON, JSON-LD contains contextual information in the form of URIs/IRIs for vocabularies, schemas, and ontologies, enabling machine semantic interpretation of the information. The PID of the concept must also be included as a web link.

Green: At least one of the formats mentioned is available via an interface or as a download.

Yellow: None of the formats mentioned are available. However, other common machine-readable formats, such as XML (but not RDF), are offered. These have reduced semantic expressiveness for machine evaluation and can increase the effort required to prepare the data.

Red: None of the formats mentioned are available.

2.11 At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1)

The community standard for vocabularies is implemented when SKOS and OWL serialisations are offered. These are internationally recognised formal languages used to encode documentation systems, such as controlled vocabularies and ontologies.

If the vocabulary is a thesaurus, it should be structured in accordance with [ISO 25964](#), [DIN 1463](#), or [ANSI/NISO Z39.19-2005 \(R2010\)](#).

Green: At least one SKOS/OWL format is available. If it is a thesaurus, it must conform to the specified standards.

Yellow: At least one SKOS/OWL format is available.

AND: If it is a thesaurus, there is no conformity with any of the specified standards.

OR: No SKOS/OWL format is available. If it is a thesaurus, then it conforms to one of the specified standards.

Red: No SKOS/OWL format is available. If it is a thesaurus, there is no conformity with any of the specified standards.

2.12 The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2)

Mapping establishes relationships between concepts with similar meanings in different vocabularies. Mappings are considered 'qualified' if the type of relationship between the concepts is documented, too. This is typically achieved by using [SKOS Mapping Properties](#) to indicate the degree of agreement between the two concepts.

Green: There are occasional mappings to at least one other vocabulary that offers URIs for its concepts and is openly licensed. If the number of mappings appears low, the editorial team should have stated their intention to fill this gap.

The mappings are contained in SKOS or OWL, in at least one machine-readable serialisation. They always contain the URI of the target concept. For generic concept vocabularies, information on the mapping property is included. The mappings do not have to cover the entire concept set of the vocabulary.

Yellow: There are mappings to at least one other vocabulary, but these are not contained in SKOS or OWL in a machine-readable format. Either they do not contain the URIs of the target concept, or the target vocabulary does not use URIs.

For vocabularies with generic concepts, mapping properties are not included.

The target vocabulary either does not offer machine-readable serialisations, or it has restricted access. This would make the automated creation of links based on the mappings relatively complex.

These mappings are not available in the actual vocabulary service itself, but from another provider (e.g. Wikidata).

Red: No mappings available.

2.13 The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1)

In addition to the general licence information available on the vocabulary provider's website, the licence should also be included in serialisations of data made available via interfaces or downloads. Ideally, it should be provided in the form of a URI.

The licence information provided by the vocabulary provider is authoritative. If there is conflicting information in other sources (e.g. a registry), this will be noted in the comments.

Green: The licence is specified in human-readable format on the website or in a PDF, at least at the vocabulary level. It is also included in at least one machine-readable serialisation, ideally alongside the licence's URI. The licence information can be found there in the vocabulary dataset itself, in the header of a structured download file, or in each concept data record.

Yellow: The licence is specified by the provider in human-readable form, at least at the vocabulary level. However, it is not included in the machine-readable serialisations.

OR The licence is only included in one machine-readable serialisation, but not in primarily human-readable presentations at the vocabulary or concept level.

Red: The licence is not specified on the website at the vocabulary or concept level, nor in at least one serialisation.

2.14 Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1)

In order to help users assess whether a vocabulary meets their scientific requirements and is suitable for their purposes, the metadata should include information about the creation date, creator, editor and version, licence, target domain, and a brief description. The metadata should also describe the concept's change history, the definition's source, and other metadata. Information on the vocabulary's development history, growth, conformity with certain standards, adaptation or integration of other vocabularies or on previous versions, and on current editorial activity should also be available.

Green: The vocabulary provider offers comprehensive information on the creation and expansion of the vocabulary, enabling users to make an informed decision on its suitability for their purposes. This includes information on technical coverage and granularity, structural characterisation, the underlying standard (e.g. [ISO 25964](#)), the editorial team's working methods and guidelines, and the continuity of the service. Interfaces and data dumps must be easy to find and well documented.

As there is currently no established standard for providing this type of metadata in machine-readable format, human-readable format is sufficient. Published sources that are not directly available from the provider can also be used to learn about the vocabulary's history.

Yellow: Although the vocabulary provider offers some metadata, essential aspects listed under 'green' are missing and cannot be obtained from other published sources without considerable effort.

Red: The vocabulary provider provides little to no meta information, and it cannot be obtained from other published sources with reasonable effort.

2.15 The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3)

A vocabulary meets community standards if its coverage and level of differentiation (granularity) satisfy the information requirements of a specific subject area at an expert level. Certain areas that are not yet sufficiently differentiated can be added, if necessary, at the initiative of the community.

Generally, community standards in the museum and collection sector are not formally established. They manifest themselves primarily in common application practices. For example, there is a consensus on which information should be covered by a controlled vocabulary and which vocabulary is suitable for this purpose. [ISO 25964](#), [DIN 1463](#), [ANSI/NISO Z39.19-2005 \(R2010\)](#), SKOS and OWL are all examples of comprehensive community standards for modelling the structure and content of knowledge information systems.

Due to the varying requirements of users, it is difficult to define this criterion precisely. For example, archaeologists, ethnologists, provenance researchers, conservators and restorers have different documentation priorities and require different technical terms compared to those working in collection cataloguing or inventorying. Our assessment is based on standard documentation requirements for art and cultural history collections, focusing on the data elements for which the vocabulary is suitable (see the corresponding table rows). The scenario does not include minimum or preliminary cataloguing, as this should also be carried out using sufficiently differentiated vocabulary to allow for expansion at a later stage, initially focusing only on core information.

Green: The vocabulary covers concepts and terms in the technical specificity required by experts, with regard to breadth and granularity. It is suitable for a differentiated description of collection objects at expert-level, according to [CDWA](#), [CCO](#), [Spectrum](#) and [LIDO](#) standards.

Yellow: The vocabulary frequently covers concepts and terms with the level of detail required by experts. In some areas, there is a lack of differentiation. This may mean that concepts and terms are unavailable or that available terms are not clearly distinguished from other, unsuitable homonyms, which can lead to misunderstandings and incorrect usage.

Red: The vocabulary does not meet the requirements for the specified data elements in the collection documentation, or only meets them to a limited extent.

2.16 Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1)

Definitions and explanations of the concept are necessary to explain and clarify its meaning and to distinguish it from other related or confusingly similar concepts. They ensure that concepts in the controlled vocabulary are used consistently across different databases.

Green: Thesauri: The definitions provided for most concepts (including scope notes and descriptions) accurately convey their meaning. Where appropriate, they also distinguish the concept from easily confusable concepts or provide references to related concepts. If not all concepts have been defined, the editorial team should state their intention to fill this gap.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: All concepts are correctly positioned in the classification tree. The meaning can be reliably determined from the hierarchical context of the concept.

Vocabularies for individual entities: The entity description contains sufficient attributes to reliably identify and distinguish the entity from others with the same or similar names.

Yellow: Thesauri: A significant proportion of the vocabulary lacks definitions, and there is no indication that this issue is being prioritised. However, the meaning of the concepts can be determined from their hierarchical classification or other information provided in the concept data records.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: Concepts are correctly positioned in the classification tree. The meaning can usually be reliably determined from the hierarchical context of the concept, but sometimes this is not possible.

Vocabularies for individual entities: The description of the majority of entities contains enough attributes to reliably identify and distinguish them from items with the same or similar names.

Red: Thesauri: The vocabulary provides few or no definitions for its concepts, and there is no indication that the editorial team is prioritising this work. The meaning of the concepts is also not apparent from the hierarchical classification or other information in the data record.

Definitions that have been extensively developed and updated by the editorial team have not been incorporated into third-party websites. This may also be due to the fact that these websites are updated infrequently or not at all.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: Concepts are not always positioned correctly within the classification tree. It is not possible to reliably determine the meaning from the hierarchical context of the concept..

Vocabularies for individual entities: The description of most entities does not contain enough attributes to reliably identify and distinguish them from items with the same or similar names.

2.17 The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1)

When concepts as units of thought are represented solely by verbal designations, users may interpret them differently depending on their prior knowledge. A term may have multiple meanings, or a single concept may be represented by multiple terms. To ensure the term is used as precisely as possible, a series of attributes should be provided for each concept to convey exactly what the concept is and how it can be distinguished from similar ones.

Green: Thesauri: The vocabulary contains definitions (see the above assessment). It also offers synonyms (terms with the same or very similar meanings), language variants, mappings, references, examples of usage and illustrations. While not all of these features need to be implemented, they should be consistently available throughout the vocabulary.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: The vocabulary has a consistent, hierarchical structure that clarifies the meaning of terms in context. It also provides definitions or descriptions, synonyms (terms with the same or very similar meanings), language variants, mappings, references, examples of usage and illustrations. While not all of these features need to be implemented, they should be present frequently throughout the vocabulary.

Vocabularies for individual entities: The description of the vast majority of entities contains enough name variants or references to related objects and sources to support interpretation and reuse.

Yellow: Thesauri: The vocabulary contains definitions, as well as synonyms, language variants, mappings, references, application examples and illustrations. However, these are sometimes insufficient in terms of quantity or quality to support the correct use of the terms.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: The vocabulary has a consistent hierarchical structure that always conveys the meaning of the concept in context. Occasionally, it may also offer definitions or descriptions, synonyms, language variants, mappings, references, examples of use or illustrations. If this is not the case, this does not result in a downgrade.

Vocabularies for individual entities: The description of various entities contains enough name variants or references to related items and sources to support interpretation and reuse.

Red: Thesauri: The vocabulary provides few or no definitions for its concepts, synonyms, language variants, mappings, references, application examples or illustrations. This means that the correct usage of the terms is essentially left to the user's interpretation, as it is not supported.

Definitions and attributes that have been extensively developed and updated by the editorial team have not been incorporated into third-party websites. This may also be due to the fact that these websites are updated infrequently or not at all.

Classifications, taxonomies, etc.: The vocabulary does not consistently feature a hierarchical structure that secures the meaning of the concept in context. Nor does it offer any definitions or descriptions, synonyms, language variants, mappings, references, application examples or illustrations that support the interpretation and reuse of the concepts.

Vocabularies for individual entities: Few, if any, of the entities contain enough name variants or references to related items and sources to enable the term to be interpreted and reused.

3. The vocabularies in detail: description and FAIR assessment

3.1 Thesaurus of Agricultural Tools <i>[Ackerbaugeräte-Thesaurus]</i>	
Brief description	<p>The Thesaurus of Agricultural Tools (Ackerbaugeräte-Thesaurus) is a polyhierarchical thesaurus of names for agricultural and woodworking equipment and vehicles.</p> <p>It is the result of the 'Kleine Museen' (Small Museums) project, which was carried out by the Institut für Museumskunde [now: Institut für Museumsforschung] Berlin, Landschaftsverband Rheinland, and the Rheinisches Landesmuseum Bonn between 1984 and 1988. It was first published in 1988. W. Eckehart Spengler. Thesaurus zu Ackerbaugerät, Feldbestellung – Landwirtschaftliche Transport- und Nutzfahrzeuge – Werkzeuge (Holzbearbeitung), 2. unveränderte Auflage, Berlin 2000</p> <p>The thesaurus was created in accordance with DIN 1463 (ISO 2788).</p> <p>The vocabulary is available on both museum-digital and museumsvokabular.de. The two sites are not synchronised.</p> <p>The references to literature for concepts and terms contained in the original publication were not included in museum-digital md:term or in the experimental SkoHub implementation of museumsvokabular.de.</p>
Web link	<p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/ackerbaugerate-systematik/ SkoHub: https://museumsvokabular-de.github.io/Museumsvokabular-Hub/ackerbau.html museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	<p>museumsvokabular.de: 929 (PDF, 2025-07-25) 1.050 (RDF XML, 2025-07-25)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: 1.664 (2025-11-19)</p>

Languages	German
License	museumsvokabular.de: CC BY-NC-SA 2.0 DE museum-digital md:term: not specified
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Institut für Museumsforschung, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin (SPK); museum-digital
Editorial team active?	No
Web link documentation	Structure, content: https://www.smb.museum/fileadmin/website/Institute/Institut_fuer_Museumsforschung/Publikationen/Mitteilungen/MIT019.pdf
Community contributions possible?	No
Interfaces / Data Transfer	museumsvokabular.de: download https://museumsvokabular.de/ackerbaugerate-systematik/ SkoHub: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/downloads REST API: https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/
Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/ackerbau/reconciliation/tag?lang=de
Available data formats / serialisations	museumsvokabular.de: RDF XML, museumvok-XML with DTD and documentation SkoHub: JSON. Turtle is also available on the GitHub page: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub . However, this is not an official museumsvokabular.de service.
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/497 LOV: not available (2025-11-19) FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-19) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/ackerbaugerate-systematik/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190549 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126950719
Suitable for field of specialisation	Ethnology, history, cultural history

Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation <i>museumsvokabular.de: The SkoHub implementation is not yet included in the standard service offer. Therefore, it is not included in the FAIRness assessment.</i>
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Only in the experimental SkoHub implementation, the vocabulary itself can be referenced directly by an identifier. Otherwise, it can only be addressed indirectly via either the Wikidata or registry entries.
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: In the standard service, it is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. This is only possible indirectly via either entries in Wikidata or the registries.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	red	museumsvokabular.de: The available download formats use the preferred term as the identifier; no formatting as a URL. SkoHub: The preferred term is used as the ID and is supplemented by a URL component.
	green	museum-digital md:term: provided
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Human users can search for the vocabulary. Additional software is required to search the download formats. Additional functionalities are only available via the SkoHub implementation.
	green	museum-digital md:term: provided
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3)	green	

more info		
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	red	museumsvokabular.de: No dereferencing to the vocabulary or its concepts is possible. This is only provided via the SkoHub implementation.
	green	museum-digital md:term: provided
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The vocabulary can be found via web browsers and entry in BARTOC. The individual concepts can only be searched in the SkoHub implementation.
	green	museum-digital md:term: provided
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Creation date of the dataset specified in RDF XML and PDF. Modification data is missing.
	green	museum-digital md:term: Last modification date in the web display and in JSON format, not included in RDF.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1)	green	museumsvokabular.de: RDF XML with SKOS
	green	museum-digital md:term: RDF XML with SKOS

more info		
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	The Thesaurus of Agricultural Tools contains no mappings to other vocabularies. There is also no corresponding Wikidata mapping property.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	museumsvokabular.de: Clear labelling. The licence information with URI is included in the RDF download file, but not in the other serialisations.
	red	museum-digital md:term: No indication of a licence on the website or in the serialisations provided.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Information on the origin of the vocabulary is only available in the PDF of the original publication. The structure and maintenance of the service is largely undocumented.
	red	museum-digital md:term: Origin, structure and maintenance of the service is largely undocumented.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	There are no definitions throughout. Usually, the hierarchical arrangement of concepts within the vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation.

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>museumsvokabular.de: Definitions, examples of use and cross-references are missing. There are also a large number of alternative terms, including terms from regional dialects. The hierarchical arrangement of concepts within the vocabulary usually helps to clarify contextualisation.</p> <p>Bibliographical references from the original publication were not included in the PDF or SkoHub implementation, but they are contained in RDF format.</p>
	<p>yellow</p>	<p>museum-digital md:term: Definitions, examples of use and cross-references are missing. There are also a large number of alternative terms, including terms from regional dialects. Usually, the hierarchical arrangement of concepts within the vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation.</p> <p>Bibliographical references from the original publication were not included.</p>

3.2 Typology of Vessels [*Gefäßtypologie*]

<p>Brief description</p>	<p>The Typology of Vessels (Gefäßtypologie) deals with the names given to objects based on their form and function. It covers vessels from the 15th century onwards and provides a classification system with formal descriptions of objects, explanatory material, technical information and synonyms. This classification is based on the illustrated publication by Werner Endres: Gefäße und Formen. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen. München 1996 (vergriffen).</p> <p>It is part of the Object Naming File and is being further developed there: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://obg.vocnet.org/&startNode=x000857x (section in digiCULT xTree.public) and http://obg.vocnet.org/x000857x (section within the Object Naming File).</p> <p>However, separate versions of the vocabulary dating back to 2006 are available and are no longer actively maintained, and therefore differ in content and scope. These are available in the form of a PDF file with illustrations and an experimental presentation of the concepts in SkoHub at museumsvokabular.de.</p>
<p>Web link</p>	<p>Vessels in Object Naming File at digiCULT xTree.public: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=htt</p>

	<p>p://obg.vocnet.org/&startNode=x000857x</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/gefaesstypologie/ SkoHub implementation: https://museumsvokabular-de.github.io/Museumsvokabular-Hub/gefaess.html</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: 425 (2025-11-13)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: PDF: 364 (2025-11-13) RDF XML download: 416 (2025-11-13) museumvok-XML download: 416 (2025-11-13) SkoHub implementation: 416 (2025-11-13)</p>
Languages	German
License	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: CC BY 4.0</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: CC BY-NC-SA 2.0 DE</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher and editorial board: Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern
Editorial team active?	<p>Active development in digiCULT xTree.public as part of the Object Naming File (see chapter) and the respective xTree area.</p> <p>The version available at museumsvokabular.de will not be further developed.</p>
Web link documentation	-
Community contributions possible?	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: Suggestions for revision can be sent to the Landesstelle für nichtstaatliche Museen in Bayern.</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: no options</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: REST API (exclusively for institutions within the cooperative): https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/docs/xTree_rest_0.86.pdf; RDF data dumps of the entire Object Naming File are made available.</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: download https://museumsvokabular.de/gefaesstypologie/ and SkoHub: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub</p>
Mapping services	
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: PDF, RDF XML, museumvok-XML;</p>

	SkoHub implementation: JSON. SkoHub: JSON. RDF XML and Turtle are also available on the GitHub page: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub . However, this is not an official museumsvokabular.de service.	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/491 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-20) LOV: not available (2025-11-20) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/gefaesstypologie/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190545 Wikidata: https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q136706277	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation <i>museumsvokabular.de: The SkoHub implementation is not yet included in the standard service offer. Therefore, it is not included in the FAIRness assessment.</i>
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: In the standard service, it is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. This is only possible indirectly via either entries in Wikidata or the registries. It is also possible in the SkoHub implementation.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1)	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Each concept in the available download files has an identifier. However, this identifier does not have the form

more info		of a URL and cannot be supplemented using a base URL. Example: gefaess/00000026.
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: A search for terms is only possible indirectly in the download files. The experimental SkoHub implementation allows you to search for terms and concepts.
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The download formats do not contain identifiers in the form of URIs; only a human-readable representation is provided. A machine-readable representation is only available through the experimental SkoHub implementation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The vocabulary is indexed in Wikidata and in registries. Concepts and terms are not indexed individually in the standard service. However, individual terms can be searched for using the SkoHub implementation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: There is no versioning. While the creation date of the data record is included in the serialisations, no modification

		date is provided. Therefore, it can be assumed that the offer has not been updated since it was made available.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museumsvokabular.de
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public: Mappings available, extension is planned
	red	museumsvokabular.de: No mappings available. There is also no corresponding Wikidata mapping property.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: The licence information is included in the RDF XML serialisation only, not in the human-readable presentation of the vocabulary.
	green	museumsvokabular.de
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Information on creation of the vocabulary, maintenance and editorial guidelines not available.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3)	green	

more info		
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	Although some definitions are missing, the meaning of concepts can easily be deduced by their place in the vocabulary hierarchy. The existing definitions are largely sufficient for using the terms correctly.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	In the offerings of digiCULT xTree.public and museumsvokabular.de some definitions are missing. museumsvokabular.de includes references to illustrations in the original publication in the data, but the illustrations are not accessible.

3.3 Integrated Authority File [*Gemeinsame Normdatei, GND*]

Brief description	<p>The Integrated Authority File (Gemeinsame Normdatei, GND) is a service that facilitates the collaborative use and management of authority data. This data represents and describes entities such as persons, corporate bodies, conferences, geographical features, generic concepts (subject headings), and works related to cultural and scientific collections. In particular, libraries use the GND to index publications. However, archives, museums, cultural and scientific institutions, as well as scientists and researchers working on research projects are also increasingly making use of the GND.</p> <p>The GND is offered via several services. The offerings are synchronised with the authoritative dataset of the German National Library (Deutsche Nationalbibliothek, DNB) hourly at Lobid and continuously at the Bibliotheksservice-Zentrum Baden-Württemberg (BSZ).</p>
Web link	<p>GND Network (DNB): https://gnd.network/Webs/gnd/EN/Home/home_node.html</p> <p>GND Explorer: https://explore.gnd.network/</p> <p>GND at lobid (HBZ): https://lobid.org/gnd</p> <p>Online GND (OGND, BSZ): https://wiki.bsz-bw.de/pages/viewpage.action?pageId=4886299 (online search)</p>

Coverage of entities	persons, corporate bodies, conferences, geographical entities (including buildings), generic concepts for objects/works, works
Size (number of concepts)	10.162.672 (2025-11-25)
Languages	German; name variants for individual entities also in other languages; generic concepts (subject headings) contain numerous mappings to English or French library subject headings
License	CC0 1.0 Universal
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	GND cooperative (German National Library, German-speaking library associations with associated libraries, Zeitschriftendatenbank, numerous other institutions)
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://gnd.network/Webs/gnd/DE/UeberGND/ueberGND_node.html Vom Suchen und Finden – Einführung in die Recherche mit der Gemeinsamen Normdatei (2024) GND ontology: https://d-nb.info/standards/elementset/gnd
Community contributions possible?	By taking part in the cooperative (see above); by GND web form (registration required, https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Standardisierung/GND/gnd_Webformular/gnd_webformular.html) By the authority data services of the Specialised Information Services (Fachinformationsdienste, FIDs) Art (https://www.arthistoricum.net/en/service/normdatenservice-ku-nst), Performing Arts (https://www.performing-arts.eu/en/services/gnd/) and Musicology (https://www.musiconn.de/en/services/musiconnnormdatenservice) Modifications by trained staff only
Interfaces / Data Transfer	OAI-PMH, SRU (read), SRU Record Update (write), SFTP, Download via https://data.dnb.de/opendata/ Available as Entity Facts (machine-readable 'fact sheets' on GND entities): https://www.dnb.de/EN/Professionell/Metadatendienste/Datenbezug/Entity-Facts/entityFacts_node.html lobid GND API: https://lobid.org/gnd/api
Mapping services	lobid OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://lobid.org/gnd/reconcile/ Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%3A

	<p>2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F430</p> <p>NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F430</p> <p>TS4NFDI Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/ts4nfdi/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F430</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	MARC21, MARC-XML, RDF XML, JSON-LD, Turtle, HDT, N-Triples, CSV, DNB Casual (oai_dc), MODS-XML, HTML
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/430</p> <p>LOV: https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/gndo (GND Ontology)</p> <p>FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.8337e2</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/gemeinsame-normdatei-gnd/</p> <p>R:hovono: geographical entities: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190622, corporate bodies and conferences: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190621, persons: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190623, generic concepts: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190624</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q36578</p> <p>ISIL: https://isil.staatsbibliothek-berlin.de/isil/?isil=DE-588</p>
Suitable for field of specialisation	Suitable for use across disciplines, e.g., for archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science, science/technology
Suitable for MDS elements	Object title or name , Object type or designation , Classification , Materials , Techniques , Person/corporate body , Place , Subject keyword , Rights holder of media file , Repository of object , Institution providing record
Suitable for additional elements	Published Object Identifier , Related Work Set/Related Work/Object/ Object Identifier
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana , Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek , Collections from Colonial Contexts , museum-digital
Comments	-
FAIRness	

	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over	green	

time. (A.2) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	A subset of the generic concepts (subject headings) has mappings to the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH), to the Répertoire d'autorité-matière encyclopédique et alphabétique unifié (RAMEAU), to the Thesaurus of the Social Sciences (TheSoz), to the STW Thesaurus of Economics and to the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) https://wiki.dnb.de/display/GND/GND-Mappings+zu+externen+Thesauri Increasing integration of Wikidata mappings. Wikidata mapping property 'GND ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P227
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	Licence information is not included in all serialisations of the data. JSON-LD Entity Facts: included, MARC XML: not included
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	Editorial guidelines are documented: https://gnd.network/Webs/gnd/DE/UeberGND/GNDRegeln/regeln_node.html , https://sta.dnb.de/doc/GND The GND Explorer provides basic information werden on the metadata of the authority record.

		Example: https://explore.gnd.network/gnd/4049185-7
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	For persons, corporate bodies, geographical entities
	yellow	Generic concepts (subject headings) often do not yet meet the required level of specificity for collection documentation.
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	For persons, corporate bodies, geographical entities
	yellow	Generic concepts (subject headings): Descriptions of the meaning of the concept are often missing here. Instead, the meaning must be deduced from the GND Subject Categories (GND-Systematik), or any superordinate concepts or references. This requires the user to have prior specific knowledge. Works: Musical and written works are usually categorised and filterable. This is not the case for works of other genres. The concept data record often lacks the relevant information, making it unclear whether a work belongs to literature, the visual arts, or the performing arts, for example.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	For persons, corporate bodies, geographical entities
	yellow	For generic concepts (subject headings) and works: see above

3.4 GeoNames

Brief description	<p>This is an openly licensed, freely accessible geographical database with worldwide coverage.</p> <p>GeoNames aggregates data from a variety of free and public sources, providing the options to find, obtain, manually edit and enrich data via a wiki-based web interface. Additionally, GeoNames maintains its own ontology containing toponyms.</p> <p>Alongside the freely accessible service, the provider offers a data subscription that enables users to obtain a consistency-checked version of the data. Revenue from this and other commercial geodata services helps to fund GeoNames.</p>
Web link	https://www.geonames.org/
Coverage of entities	geographical entities (including buildings)
Size (number of concepts)	Over 13 million entities, including 4.8 million populated places, with over 25 million names (2025-11-26)
Languages	Platform in English. Name variants of geographic entities are available in various languages. In total, 279 languages are used; ⁸ Full text search on georeferenced Wikipedia articles in English, Dutch, German, French, Spanish, Italian, Polish, Russian, Portuguese and Chinese.
License	CC BY 4.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Publisher: Unxos GmbH Switzerland</p> <p>Editorial board: Unxos GmbH and crowdsourced editing</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Aggregated sources: https://www.geonames.org/datasources/</p> <p>Webservices: https://www.geonames.org/export/web-services.html https://www.geonames.org/export/ws-overview.html</p> <p>API: https://www.geonames.org/source-code/javadoc/</p> <p>Ontology https://www.geonames.org/ontology/documentation.html</p>
Community contributions possible?	Yes, further information: https://www.geonames.org/manual.html
Interfaces / Data Transfer	REST API

⁸ <https://www.geonames.org/wikipedia/>

Mapping services	https://fornpunkt.se/apis/reconciliation/geonames	
Available data formats / serialisations	XML, RDF XML, JSON, TXT, CSV (country information only)	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/1674, ontology: http://bartoc.org/en/node/17984</p> <p>FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.56a0Uj, Ontology: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6dba71</p> <p>LOV: Ontology: https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/gn</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/art-architecture-thesaurus-aat/ (2025-12-12)</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1194736</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q830106</p>	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science, science/technology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Place , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	When the object in focus is a building: Published Object Identifier , Related Work Set/Related Work/Object/ Object Identifier	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana , Collections from Colonial Contexts , museum-digital	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web	green	

<p>identifier. (F.4) more info</p>		
<p>The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info</p>	green	
<p>When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info</p>	green	
<p>Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1)</p>	green	

more info		
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	yellow	References to Wikipedia and DBpedia. Otherwise, no mappings available. Wikidata mapping property 'GeoNames ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1566 .
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	Given the lack of a central editorial team (for the free version), overall quality depends in part on the quality of the entries or sources. However, the locations are identifiable thanks to the provided geocoordinates.

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>Given the lack of a central editorial team (for the free version), specificity depends in part on the quality of the entries or sources. However, the locations are identifiable thanks to the provided geocoordinates.</p>
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<h3>3.5 Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)</h3>	
<p>Brief description</p>	<p>A polyhierarchically structured thesaurus comprising generic concepts relating to art, architecture, and cultural heritage. It contains a comprehensive range of specialist vocabulary, covering types of works and objects, materials, agents, activities, styles and periods, as well as brand names and associated concepts. These entities are supplied with descriptions, multilingual terms, references, and source information.</p> <p>The AAT is developed and expanded in accordance with the international thesaurus standard ISO 25964. It has an excellent reputation and is used worldwide by memory institutions.</p> <p>AAT-Deutsch provides German terms and descriptions for some of the concepts, particularly in the object facet. The Swiss Art Research Infrastructure (SARI) is also creating an AAT instance featuring German, Italian and French terms.</p>
<p>Web link</p>	<p>https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/</p> <p>AAT-Deutsch: https://www.aat-deutsch.de/ (online search)</p> <p>DANTE: https://dante.gbv.de/pool/person_role (roles of persons only)</p>
<p>Coverage of entities</p>	<p>Generic concepts for objects/works</p>
<p>Size (number of concepts)</p>	<p>74.460 (503.230 terms) (2025-11-19)</p> <p>DANTE: 857 (role of person, 2025-11-19)</p>
<p>Languages</p>	<p>American English Incomplete in different degrees of coverage: British English,</p>

	German, Dutch, Spanish, French, Italian, Chinese, Swedish, Greek, Ancient Greek etc.
License	Getty: ODC-By 1.0 DANTE: CC0 1.0 Universal
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: J. Paul Getty Trust Editorial board: Getty Research Institute Contributions via international cooperations, e.g., by the editorial board of AAT-Deutsch
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	Structure, content: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/about.html Linked Open Data: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lod/index.html Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology: https://vocab.getty.edu/ontology Reuse, technical aspects: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html
Community contributions possible?	Yes, contributions of varying amounts after conclusion of Data Contribution and License Agreement; according to AAT editorial guidelines; via table format, web form, XML, see https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/contribute.html Editorial guidelines: https://www.getty.edu/publications/vocabularies-editorial-guidelines/aat-guidelines/ Translations in AAT-Deutsch: https://www.aat-deutsch.de/ Swiss Art and Architecture Thesaurus Translation Project: https://www.sari.uzh.ch/de/Projekte/das-swiss-art-and-architecture-thesaurus-translation-projekt.html
Interfaces / Data Transfer	SPARQL, webservice, database extract to download: documentation: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html
Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://services.getty.edu/vocab/reconcile/ OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/openrefine.html
Available data formats /	Getty: JSON, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples

serialisations	relational tables, XML DANTE: JSKOS, MARC-XML, MARC-JSON, Turtle, N-Triples	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/75 FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.LQfdaV LOV: https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/gvp (Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/art-architecture-thesaurus-aat/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190526 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q611299	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Materials , Techniques , Measurements (Measurement Type) Subject keyword (type of subject object), Media file: type of media file	
Suitable for additional elements	Title Set : Type of Title Set, Role Actor , Attribution Qualifier Actor Inscriptions/Marks : Type of Inscription/Mark, Culture , Period/Style , Description/Descriptive Note Set : Type of Description/Descriptive Note Set	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana , Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek , Collections from Colonial Contexts	
Comments	https://www.aat-deutsch.de/ provides approx. 9.000 concepts with German terms, which for the most part have been integrated into the Getty AAT (2025-11-25).	
FAIRness		
	Assess-ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and	green	

output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info		
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	See Semantic View, elements: dcterms:created, dcterms:modified, skos:changeNote, dcterms:contributor
	green	DANTE: creation and modification date in concept data record and in JSKOS format
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with	green	

SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info		
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	Integration of Wikidata mappings. Wikidata mapping property 'AAT ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1014
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	Getty AAT: included in web representation and serialisations.
	green	DANTE: licence information differs from the publisher's statement.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
	yellow	DANTE: little information, but a clear reference to the source of the vocabulary
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	Structure conforming to ISO 25964; see editorial process and quality management for new terms and concepts
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms,	green	

synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info		
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3.6 Getty Cultural Objects Name Authority (CONA)

Brief description	<p>Hierarchically structured thesaurus of visual and architectural works, as well as ceremonial and functional objects from the field of material culture. It covers all eras and cultures worldwide.</p> <p>Entries contain titles, names and information about manufacturers, as well as details of physical characteristics, depicted themes and locations and other information about the respective works.</p> <p>CONA is not yet complete. As a compiled resource, it grows through contributions from third parties.</p> <p>The vocabulary is developed and expanded in accordance with the international thesaurus standard ISO 25964.</p>
Web link	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/cona/
Coverage of entities	Works (including buildings)
Size (number of concepts)	84.340 (106.370 titles/names, 2025-11-19)
Languages	American English; titles and title variants partly with language attributes
License	ODC-By 1.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: J. Paul Getty Trust Editorial board: Getty Research Institute
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Structure, content: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/cona/about.html</p> <p>Webservice: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html</p> <p>Reuse, technical aspects: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html</p>

Community contributions possible?	<p>Yes, contributions of varying amounts after conclusion of Data Contribution and License Agreement; according to CONA editorial guidelines; via table format, XML. To maintain quality standards, all contributions undergo a review process prior to publication.</p> <p>Contributions: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/contribute.html</p> <p>Editorial Guidelines: https://www.getty.edu/publications/vocabularies-editorial-guidelines/cona-guidelines/</p>	
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>Webservice, documentation: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html</p>	
Mapping services	-	
Available data formats / serialisations	-	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/94</p> <p>FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.reeng1</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/cultural-objects-name-authority-cona/</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1752656</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q11409212</p>	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Subject keyword (type of work/object as a subject)	
Suitable for additional elements	Published Object Identifier , Related Work Set/Related Work/Object/ Object Identifier	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	unknown	
Comments	As coverage is still relatively low, usefulness for authority data referencing of cultural objects is still limited.	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation

<p>The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info</p>	<p>red</p>	<p>No versioning information</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info</p>	<p>red</p>	<p>RDF or JSON-LD serialisations not yet available</p>
<p>At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>Structure conforming to ISO 25964, RDF or JSON-LD serialisations not yet available</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>CONA does not include mappings to other vocabularies. Wikidata mapping property 'Cultural Objects Names ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1669</p>
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The licence is neither displayed in the data record for each concept nor delivered via the web service.</p>
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The vocabulary is developed conforming to ISO 25964, see editorial process and quality management for new terms and concepts. As this vocabulary is in development, coverage is still limited.</p>

Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.7 Getty Iconography Authority (IA)

Brief description	<p>Hierarchically structured thesaurus of subjects in visual art. It includes proper names and other information about the events, themes and narratives from religion/mythology, legendary and fictional characters, subjects from literature, works of literature and the performing arts, and legendary and fictional places dealt with in a work.</p> <p>The IA's coverage is multilingual, multicultural and global. It is not limited to Western iconography, but is culturally global in scope. Concepts, terms and names covered by the AAT, TGN, ULAN and CONA are excluded.</p> <p>As a compiled resource, it grows through contributions from third parties.</p> <p>IA is developed and expanded in accordance with the international thesaurus standard ISO 25964.</p>
Web link	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/cona/
Coverage of entities	Subjects
Size (number of concepts)	7.050 (7.445 names/terms, 2025-11-19)
Languages	American English; name variants and terms partly with language attributes
License	ODC-By 1.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: J. Paul Getty Trust

	Editorial board: Getty Research Institute
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Structure, content: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/cona/about.html</p> <p>Webservice: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html</p> <p>Reuse, technical aspects: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html</p>
Community contributions possible?	<p>Yes, contributions of varying amounts after conclusion of Data Contribution and License Agreement; according to CONA editorial guidelines; via table format, XML. See: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/contribute.html</p> <p>Editorial guidelines: https://www.getty.edu/publications/vocabularies-editorial-guidelines/ia-guidelines/</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>Webservice, documentation: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html</p>
Mapping services	-
Available data formats / serialisations	-
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>FAIRsharing: as part of CONA https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.reenq1</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>museumsvocabular.de: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>R:hovono: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q43187601</p>
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history, art
Suitable for MDS elements	Subject keyword
Suitable for additional elements	-
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-

Comments	Coverage is still too limited, even for well-known iconographic subjects.	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	Although the vocabulary is part of CONA, it has its own PID .
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2)	green	

more info		
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	red	No versioning information
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	red	RDF or JSON-LD serialisations not yet available
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	yellow	Structure conforming to ISO 25964, RDF or JSON-LD serialisations not yet available
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	IA includes mappings to other vocabularies, e.g., Iconclass. Wikidata mapping property 'Getty Iconography Authority ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P5986
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	The licence is neither displayed in the data record for each concept nor delivered via the web service.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field,	yellow	The vocabulary is developed conforming to ISO 25964, see editorial process and quality management for new terms and concepts. As this vocabulary is still in development, it often

reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info		has insufficient coverage to allow the IA to be used as the primary vocabulary for subject indexing.
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.8 Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN)

Brief description	<p>Hierarchically structured thesaurus of geographic entities.</p> <p>The TGN records political and administrative units (e.g. cities and nations) as well as natural geographical features (e.g. mountains and rivers) from around the world. Its temporal coverage ranges from prehistory to the present day.</p> <p>It provides the names, relationships, location types and coordinates of places needed to document, discover and retrieve comprehensive information about art, architecture and other cultural heritage objects. The interests of related disciplines, such as archaeology and monument preservation, are also accommodated.</p> <p>The vocabulary is not yet complete. As a compiled resource, it grows through contributions from third parties.</p> <p>It is not a geographic information system (GIS), but it can be linked to geographic databases and maps. Although most entries in the TGN contain geographic coordinates, these coordinates are only approximate and serve as a reference.</p> <p>TGN is developed and expanded in accordance with the international thesaurus standard ISO 25964. It has an</p>
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	excellent reputation and is used worldwide by memory institutions.
Web link	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/
Coverage of entities	geographical entities
Size (number of concepts)	3.020.110 (5.327.275 names, 2025-11-19)
Languages	American English; place names in various languages, historic names, vernacular names, official names
License	ODC-By 1.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: J. Paul Getty Trust Editorial board: Getty Research Institute
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	Structure, content: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/about.html Linked Open Data: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lod/index.html Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology: https://vocab.getty.edu/ontology Reuse, technical aspects: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html
Community contributions possible?	Yes, contributions of varying amounts after conclusion of Data Contribution and License Agreement; according to TGN editorial guidelines; via table format, web form, XML, see: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/contribute.html Editorial guidelines: https://www.getty.edu/publications/vocabularies-editorial-guidelines/tgn-guidelines/
Interfaces / Data Transfer	SPARQL, webservice, database extract to download: documentation: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html
Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://services.getty.edu/vocab/reconcile/ OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/openrefine.html
Available data formats / serialisations	JSON, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples, relational tables, XML

Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/109 FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.1413b5 LOV: https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/gvp (Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/thesaurus-of-geographical-names-tgn/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190525 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1520117	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science	
Suitable for MDS elements	Place , Subject keyword (place as subject)	
Suitable for additional elements	Repository/Location	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	

When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	red	No versioning information
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use	yellow	TGN does not include mappings to other vocabularies.

<p>qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>		<p>Wikidata mapping property 'Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1667</p>
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	green	
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	green	<p>The vocabulary is developed conforming to ISO 25964, see editorial process and quality management for new terms and concepts.</p>
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	green	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	green	

3.9 Getty Union List of Artist Names (ULAN)

Brief description	<p>Structured vocabulary of names and other information on persons and corporate bodies.</p> <p>ULAN primarily lists creators of fine art, as well as architects, other artists, and companies and studios, both known and anonymous. It also includes clients, patrons, art collectors and creators of visual cultural objects of a ceremonial or functional nature.</p> <p>Entries contain the names, relationships and biographical information necessary for the documentation, collection and research of comprehensive information on art, architecture and other material culture.</p> <p>ULAN is developed and expanded in accordance with the international thesaurus standard ISO 25964. It has an excellent reputation and is used worldwide by memory institutions.</p>
Web link	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/ulan/
Coverage of entities	Persons and corporate bodies
Size (number of concepts)	525.300 (1.483.845 names, 2025-11-19)
Languages	American English; names of persons and corporate bodies partly with language attributes
License	ODC-By 1.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Publisher: J. Paul Getty Trust</p> <p>Editorial board: Getty Research Institute</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Structure, content: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/ulan/about.html</p> <p>Linked Open Data: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lod/index.html</p> <p>Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology: https://vocab.getty.edu/ontology</p> <p>Reuse, technical aspects: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html</p>
Community contributions possible?	Yes, contributions of varying amounts after conclusion of Data Contribution and License Agreement; according to ULAN editorial guidelines; via table format, web form, XML, see:

	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/contribute.html Editorial guidelines: https://www.getty.edu/publications/vocabularies-editorial-guidelines/ulan-guidelines/	
Interfaces / Data Transfer	SPARQL, Webservice, database extract to download: documentation: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/download.html	
Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://services.getty.edu/vocab/reconcile/ OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/openrefine.html	
Available data formats / serialisations	JSON, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples, relational tables, XML	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/118 FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.f84009 LOV: https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/vocabs/gvp (Getty Vocabulary Program Ontology) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/union-list-of-artist-names-ulan/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190518 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2494649	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Person/corporate body , Subject keyword (Person or corporate body as subject), Rights holder of media file , Repository of object , Institution providing record	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a	green	

globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info		
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are	green	See Semantic View, elements: dcterms:created, dcterms:modified, skos:changeNote,

appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info		dcterms:contributor
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	yellow	ULAN does not include mappings to other vocabularies. Wikidata mapping property 'Union List of Artist Names ID' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P245
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	The vocabulary is developed conforming to ISO 25964, see editorial process and quality management for new terms and concepts.

Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.10 General Classification for Museums [*Grobsystematik*]

Brief description	<p>The General Classification for Museums (Grobsystematik) is a result of the 'Kleine Museen' (Small Museums) project, which was carried out by the Institut für Museumskunde [now: Institut für Museumsforschung] Berlin, Museumsamt Rheinland and Museumsamt Westfalen-Lippe between 1984 and 1988. It was first published in 1988: Carlos Saro and Christof Wolters: EDV-gestützte Bestandserschließung in kleinen und mittleren Museen. Bericht zum Projekt 'Kleine Museen' für den Zeitraum 1984-1987. Berlin 1988 (Materialien aus dem Institut für Museumskunde, 24, appendix p. 35ff.).</p> <p>The vocabulary provides a general, polyhierarchical classification to aid categorisation, which was originally intended to support archives of museum authorities. However, it is also used by small and medium-sized museums for cataloguing their collections.</p> <p>The classification comprises 62 main groups, derived from function, usage context, status, material, user group, and so on.</p> <p>Some concepts overlap with those in the Object Name File (OBG), although there are differences in detail, as the OBG is continuously edited and developed.</p> <p>On museumsvoabular.de the General Classification for Museums is available to download in XML, as well as in an experimental SkoHub implementation. The vocabulary is also available on museum-digital.de in the md:term terminology service. The services are not synchronised.</p>
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Web link	<p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/grobsystematik/ SkoHub: https://museumsvokabular-de.github.io/Museumsvokabular-Hub/grobsystematik.html</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	<p>museumsvokabular.de: 9.241 (RDF XML, museumvok XML, SkoHub, 2025-11-13)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: RDF XML download: 14.832 concepts - all serialisations (2025-11-13)</p>
Languages	German
License	<p>museumsvokabular.de: CC BY-NC-SA 2.0 DE</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: not specified</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Institut für Museumskunde (now: Institut für Museumsforschung), in collaboration with Museumsamt Rheinland and Museumsamt Westfalen-Lippe
Editorial team active?	No, the project has been completed.
Web link documentation	Materialien aus dem Institut für Museumskunde; 24, 1988
Community contributions possible?	No, the project has been completed.
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>museum-digital md:term: REST API (https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)</p>
Mapping services	<p>Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/grobsystematik/reconciliation/ag?lang=de</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>museumsvokabular.de: RDF XML, museumvok XML SkoHub: JSON. Turtle is also available on the GitHub page: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub. However, this is not an official museumsvokabular.de service.</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: RDF XML, JSON-LD</p>
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/452</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-13)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-13)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/grobsystematik/</p>

	R:hovono: not available (2025-11-13) Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126952524	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology ethnology, history, cultural history, science/technology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation <i>museumsvokabular.de: The SkoHub implementation is not yet included in the standard service offer. Therefore, it is not included in the FAIRness assessment.</i>
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: In the standard service, it is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. This is only possible in the experimental SkoHub implementation. Otherwise, it can only be addressed indirectly via either entries in Wikidata or the registry BARTOC.
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: The vocabulary itself cannot be addressed directly with a unique identifier.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Each concept in the available download files has an identifier. However, this identifier does not have the form of a URL and cannot be supplemented using a base URL. For each concept, the preferred term is repeated as the identifier. This undermines the uniqueness of the identification. Example: grobsystematik/Abendtasche SkoHub: The preferred term as ID is supplemented by a URL component.

It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: A search for terms is only possible indirectly in the download files. The experimental SkoHub implementation allows you to search for terms.
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The download formats do not contain identifiers in the form of URIs; only a human-readable representation is provided. A machine-readable representation is only available through the experimental SkoHub implementation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The vocabulary is indexed in Wikidata and BARTOC. Concepts and terms are not indexed individually in the standard service. However, individual terms can be searched for using the SkoHub implementation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	museumsvokabular.de
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	museum-digital md:term
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: There is no versioning. While the creation date of the data record is included in the serialisations, there is no modification date. Therefore, it can be assumed that the offer has not been updated since it was made available.

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info</p>	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	museumsvokabular.de
<p>At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info</p>	yellow	The General Classification only partially conforms to DIN 1463 resp. ISO 25964 (lack of scope notes; no disambiguation of homonyms)
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>	red	No mappings available. There is also no corresponding Wikidata mapping property.
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	red	museum-digital md:term: no display of licence information. It is also not included in the available serialisations.
	green	museumsvokabular.de
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	yellow	Essential information on the creation of the vocabulary is provided in Materialien aus dem Institut für Museumskunde; 24, 1988 . However, information on further editorial work is missing.
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	red	<p>As the classification system was originally designed for organising museum archives, it does not cover some areas that are essential for documenting objects.</p> <p>The concepts are not defined, and homonyms are often not disambiguated.</p> <p>The hierarchical assignment of concepts within the classification system is often inconclusive in contexts outside of archiving.</p>
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1)</p>	yellow	Definitions are missing. The hierarchical structure of the vocabulary does at least provide contexts for meaning, although the assignments within the hierarchy are not

more info		always easy to understand.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	With the exception of a few synonyms, there are hardly any relevant attributes. The hierarchical arrangement of concepts within a vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation.

3.11 Nomenclature for Inventorying Cultural History Collections in Museums / Hessian Systematics [*Hessische Systematik*]

Brief description	<p>The Nomenclature for Inventorying Cultural History Collections in Museums or Hessian Systematics (Hessische Systematik) is a monohierarchical classification system for cultural history museums. It originally consisted of 18 main groups and was subdivided into subject groups and subgroups, with additional examples of objects assigned to each group. From 1993 onwards, the classification system was developed by the Museumsverband Hessen for the systematic organisation of inventory index cards. The actual determination of the museum object, including its object type, should be done separately. The 5th edition of the classification system was published in print in 2009 with 19 main groups.</p> <p>The following versions are available online:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The Museumsverband Hessen provides the 2009 print version of the 'Systematik zur Inventarisierung kulturgeschichtlicher Bestände in Museen' as PDF. It includes detailed instructions for use. 2. The 'digiCULT Hessische Systematik' currently comprises of 26 main groups and almost 1300 concepts. The object examples have not been incorporated. <p>Since 2003, the vocabulary has been adapted and extended according to the needs of the museum members of the digiCULT-Verbund eG. The vocabulary is not complete; it is maintained and expanded upon request. Editorial responsibility for the vocabulary and its contents lies with the digiCULT-Verbund eG.</p>
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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The version of the Nomenclature offered by museum-digital md:term has 20 main groups. The object examples were included as an additional level of structure in the presentation. The data was adopted on 12 February 2017. 4. museumsvokabular.de offers a PDF file generated in 2012 from the database of the Museumsverband Hessen, which contains some updates compared to the published version from 2009. 5. The DANTE service of VZG integrated the Nomenclature in 2017, based on the digiCULT version. 6. The DANTE dataset is also offered by VZG Terminology under the name of kuniweb-Sachgruppe. The VZG has supplemented it with additional entries, so in this version, it contains 19 main groups. This data extract dates from January 2023. <p>Offers 2 to 6 differ in scope and content from the original version of the Nomenclature and also differ from each other. The object examples were not included in offers 2 to 6.</p>
Web link	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Museumsverband Hessen: https://museumsverband-hessen.de/veroeffentlichung/en/downloads-bestellungen/arbeitshilfen/ (https://museumsverband-hessen.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/mvh_systematik_inventarisierung_kulturgeschichtlicher_bestande.pdf) 2. museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/hessische-systematik/ 3. digiCULT: Hessische Systematik http://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://digicult.vocnet.org/sachgruppe/&startNode=hs00148&lang=de&d=n 4. museum-digital md:term: Hessische Systematik https://term.museum-digital.de/ und https://term.museum-digital.de/hesys/tag/2771 5. VZG Terminology: kuniweb-Sachgruppe: https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/kuniweb_sachgruppe/ 6. DANTE: https://dante.gbv.de/#lists/vocabulary/e51c6ae5-9b42-4c66-ae07-e72332a178e2, concepts: https://dante.gbv.de/search?p=110
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	Museumsverband Hessen: 806 museumsvokabular.de: 845 digiCULT xTree.public: 1.295 (2025-11-21)

	<p>museum-digital md:term: 3.256 (2025-11-21)</p> <p>VZG Terminology: kuniweb-Sachgruppe: 1.091 (2025-11-21)</p> <p>DANTE: 880 (2025-11-21)</p>
Languages	German, English
License	<p>Museumsverband Hessen, digiCULT xTree.public, museum-digital md:term: not specified</p> <p>Museumsvokabular.de: CC-BY-NC-SA 2.0</p> <p>DANTE: CC-BY-SA 4.0</p> <p>VZG Terminology: CC-BY-SA 4.0</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>originally Museumsverband Hessen</p> <p>digiCULT-Verbund e.V. for the xTree.public version</p>
Editorial team active?	<p>Museumsverband Hessen: unclear</p> <p>digiCULT-Verbund e.V. for the xTree.public version</p>
Web link documentation	<p>Museumsverband Hessen: https://museumsverband-hessen.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/mvh_systematik_inventarisierung_kulturgeschichtlicher_bestande.pdf and working aid 'Inventarisieren mit der 'Hessischen Systematik' (2012), available to order for a fee.</p> <p>digiCULT: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://digicult.vocnet.org/sachgruppe/&startNode=hs00148&lang=de&d=n# (menu item 'Info')</p>
Community contributions possible?	<p>It is unclear whether requests for additions and changes can still be submitted to the editorial team via the Museumsverband Hessen.</p> <p>The digiCULT network has an editorial procedure for the xTree.public version.</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>digiCULT xTree public: Restricted access REST API for member institutions of the digiCULT association (documentation: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/docs/xTree_rest_0.86.pdf)</p> <p>VZG: REST API in DANTE (Dokumentation: https://api.dante.gbv.de/start/)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: REST API (Dokumentation: https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)</p>

Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/hesysoberbegriffsdatei/reconciliation/tag?lang=de NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F489	
Available data formats / serialisations	digiCULT xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON museum-digital md:term: RDF XML, JSON DANTE: JSKOS, MARC-XML, MARC-JSON, Turtle, N-Triples VZG Terminology: JSKOS, Turtle, RDF XML, N-Triples	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/489 (Museumsverband Hessen) and https://bartoc.org/en/node/20804 (digiCULT Hessische Systematik) FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-21) LOV: not available (2025-11-21) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/hessische-systematik/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190646 (digiCULT Hessische Systematik) Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126952483	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Ethnology, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	museum-digital	
Comments	Classification numbers for the original version are only included in PDFs from Museumsverband Hessen, museumsvokabular.de and museum-digital md:term. Other providers assign their own classification numbers. This makes it very difficult to compare the different versions. It would be helpful if the providers of the various versions could coordinate their efforts.	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent	green	digiCULT xTree.public

<p>identifier (PID). (F.1) more info</p>	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	Museumsverband Hessen
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: not directly addressable, but there is a Wikidata item and registry entries.
<p>Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info</p>	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	Museumsverband Hessen: only human-readable identifier in PDF
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: only human-readable identifier in PDF
<p>It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	red	Museumsverband Hessen: only searchable for humans. Concepts are only available in unstructured data format, as PDF.
	red	museumsvokabular.de: only searchable for humans. Concepts are only available in unstructured data format, as PDF.
<p>The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info</p>	green	
<p>When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: restricted access API
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE

required. (F.4) more info	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	Museumsverband Hessen: dereferencing for the vocabulary itself only. Concepts are only available in unstructured data format PDF.
	red	museumvokabular.de: vokabulary has no PID. Concepts are only available in unstructured data format PDF.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	Museumsverband Hessen: findable via search engine results and registry entry (BARTOC); concepts not indexed
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: vocabulary findable via search engines; concepts not indexed
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	All services
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	All services
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	Museumsverband Hessen: creation date of PDF included; no information on modifications
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: creation date of PDF included; no information on modifications

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info</p>	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	red	Museumsverband Hessen: vocabulary exclusively available as PDF
	red	museumsvokabular.de: vocabulary exclusively available as PDF
<p>At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info</p>	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE: JSKOS available
	green	VZG Terminology: JSKOS available
	red	Museumsverband Hessen: only PDF available
	red	museumsvokabular.de: only PDF available
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>	red	None of the offerings includes mappings to other vocabularies.
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	red	digiCULT xTree.public: no licence information
	red	museum-digital md:term: no licence information
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology: The licence is only included in the data record for the vocabulary itself, but not in records of the individual concepts.
	red	Museumsverband Hessen: licence information human-readable (PDF)
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: licence information human-readable (PDF)
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and</p>	yellow	All services fail to provide sufficient information on current editorial workflows. Deviating extensions are not documented adequately.

<p>maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>		
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The vocabulary contains essential concepts and terms for a specific area. Due to the uncoordinated expansion activities of various providers, the interoperability of data using the Nomenclature is limited. Some of these expansions even contradict each other. For example, in digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE and VZG Terminology, photography is a subcategory of 'Visual arts/Applied arts/Fine arts', but in museum-digital md:term, it is a separate main group with subcategories based on subject content. This does not correspond with the other categories which have been derived from usage and functional contexts.</p>
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The hierarchical arrangement of concepts within a vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation. There is a considerable number of alternative terms. All offerings except the one from Museumsverband Hessen fail to provide the object examples. These designate the correct object type of a collection item and thus help to apply the Nomenclature correctly.</p>
	<p>green</p>	<p>Museumsverband Hessen: This offering includes the object examples, and explanations on the main groups and on the practical application of the Nomenclature.</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The interpretability of the concepts is supported by the hierarchical classification system. Although there are alternative terms and language variants in some cases, there is a lack of definitions, cross-references, application examples, and mappings to other vocabularies.</p>

3.12 Hornbostel-Sachs Classification [Hornbostel-Sachs-Klassifikation]

<p>Brief description</p>	<p>Hornbostel-Sachs is a classification system for musical instruments, first published in 1914 by Erich Moritz von Hornbostel and Curt Sachs. It is the most widely used system for classifying musical instruments today. It is hierarchical and categorises instruments according to their function.</p> <p>A scan of the original 1914 version can be downloaded from the Oberlin College and Conservatory website. In 2011, the MIMO Consortium revised the classification system and made it available online in machine-readable form. The MIMO Consortium also recommends using the Thesaurus of Musical Instrument Names, in which the names of individual instruments are classified according to the Hornbostel-Sachs system.</p> <p>The Hornbostel-Sachs classification system is also available in museum-digital md:term, DANTE and Vocabs (DARIAH-EU), although the number of concepts varies considerably in each instance. The most up-to-date and complete instance appears to be the Skosmos instance from 2019, operated by MIMO, with 643 concepts.</p>
<p>Web link</p>	<p>Oberlin: digital version of the 1914 original: https://www2.oberlin.edu/faculty/rknight/Organology/H-S-1914-German.pdf</p> <p>MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: https://vocabulary.mimo-international.com/HornbostelAndSachs/de/?clang=en</p> <p>DANTE: https://dante.gbv.de/#/detail/40c78a51-3ad1-4ff6-8a96-02d74660789e</p> <p>VZG Terminology: https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/hornbostelsachs/</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/hornbostel/tag/tree#84</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/hsinstruments_thesaurus/de/</p>
<p>Coverage of entities</p>	<p>Musical instruments (classified by function)</p>
<p>Size (number of concepts)</p>	<p>Oberlin Originalversion PDF: cannot be determined</p> <p>MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: 643 (2025-10-23)</p> <p>DANTE and VZG-Terminology: 7.514 (2025-11-28)</p>

	<p>museum-digital md:term: 366 (2025-10-23)</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): 412 (2025-10-23)</p>
Languages	<p>Oberlin PDF of original version: German</p> <p>MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM version: English</p> <p>DANTE and VZG Terminology: German, English</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: English</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): German, English</p>
License	<p>DANTE and VZG Terminology: CC0 1.0 Universal</p> <p>Other services: not specified</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>MIMO (Musical Instrument Museums Online) as global consortium of museums collecting musical instruments, and ICOM-CIMCIM</p>
Editorial team active?	<p>MIMO consortium and ICOM-CIMCIM</p>
Web link documentation	<p>https://mimo-international.com/MIMO/about-mimo.aspx#frame-508</p> <p>https://cimcim.mini.icom.museum/resources/classification-of-musical-instruments/</p>
Community contributions possible?	<p>Editorial work is carried out within the MIMO consortium or at ICOM-CIMCIM.</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: download option for individual concept data records</p> <p>DANTE: REST API (https://api.dante.gbv.de/start/)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: REST API (https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): REST API (Swagger, https://vocabs-api.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/)</p>
Mapping services	<p>Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/oberbegriffsdatei/reconciliation/tag?lang=de</p> <p>Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1048</p> <p>NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1048</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: RDF XML, Turtle, JSON-LD</p>

	<p>DANTE: JSKOS, MARC-XML, MARC-JSON, Turtle, N-Triples</p> <p>VZG Terminology: JSKOS, Turtle, RDF XML, N-Triples</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: RDF XML, JSON</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): RDF XML, Turtle, JSON-LD</p>	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/1048</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-21)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-21)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/hornbostel-sachs/</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190572</p> <p>Wikidata: Hornbostel-Sachs: https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q496327, MIMO's classification of musical instruments: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q26836418</p>	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Musicology, cultural history	
Suitable for MDS elements	Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana , museum-digital	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess-ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	Oberlin
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent	yellow	Oberlin: The identifiers in the PDF are human-readable only.

<p>identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info</p>	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
<p>It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info</p>	red	Oberlin: only searchable for humans. Concepts are only available in the unstructured data format PDF.
	yellow	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: searchable for humans, and a download offering is available. For machines, searching for a term or concept is only possible to a limited extent, as no interface is available — or, at least, it cannot be found with reasonable effort.
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
<p>The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info</p>	green	
<p>When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info</p>	yellow	Oberlin: Only a human-readable representation of the vocabulary itself can be dereferenced.
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info</p>	yellow	Oberlin: The vocabulary has registry entries, individual concepts are not indexed.
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term

	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	Oberlin: PDF includes creation date; no information on modifications.
	red	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: Neither the human-readable presentation nor the serialisations indicate the last modification. Only the vocabulary level specifies a creation date. Therefore, it is not possible to determine whether updates have been made since then.
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: The human-readable presentation does not indicate the last modification. However, it is stated in the JSON-LD serialisation.
	red	Vocabs (DARIAH):Neither the human-readable presentation nor the serialisations indicate the last modification. The creation date is stated on vocabulary level, in unstructured form ('Beschreibung' in human-readable presentation, dc:description in Turtle serialisation)
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	red	Oberlin: vocabulary available exclusively as PDF
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology

	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	red	Oberlin: vocabulary available exclusively as PDF
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	None of the services presents qualified mappings to other vocabularies.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	red	Oberlin: no licence information in the PDF
	red	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM: no licence information on website or in the serialisations
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
	red	museum-digital md:term: no licence information on website or in the serialisations
	red	Vocabs (DARIAH): no licence information on website or in the serialisations
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Although essential vocabulary metadata is available, not all useful metadata is included. For example, licence information and versioning details are missing in some instances. It is also unclear which version of the source data the respective instances are based on.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects	green	In particular, the Skosmos instance operated by MIMO forms an important working basis for cataloguing musical instruments.

knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info		
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	Oberlin: definitions are sometimes missing, but the hierarchical arrangement of concepts within the vocabulary usually helps to clarify contextualisation and meaning.
	green	MIMO/ICOM-CIMCIM
	yellow	DANTE: definitions only available on the uppermost hierarchy level of the classification. While the meaning of the concepts can largely be determined by their position in the hierarchy tree, including the definitions from the original publication would have provided a more precise determination.
	green	VZG Terminology
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: definitions only available on the uppermost hierarchy level of the classification. While the meaning of the concepts can largely be determined by their position in the hierarchy tree, including the definitions from the original publication would have provided a more precise determination.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Some relevant attributes are present and the grouping within the hierarchy of this classification system appears to be consistent. However, synonyms, mappings and language variants are missing in all instances.

3.13 Iconclass

Brief description	Iconclass is a classification system for subjects relating to cultural objects. Primarily used for the subject-based indexing of visual resources and iconography, it is employed in museums, libraries, cultural history collections and art history
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	<p>projects. The system provides monohierarchically organised definitions of motifs, objects, people, events, situations and abstract concepts, represented by an alphanumeric code. This is supplemented by an extensive set of keywords and references to facilitate searching. The thematic coverage is comprehensive, ranging from alchemy to modern everyday objects, from antiquity to the present day. However, the system offers the greatest level of differentiation in traditional Western European art themes (such as ancient mythology and Christian themes and motifs).</p> <p>Iconclass is the most widely used scholarly tool for describing and locating subjects depicted in images, including works of art, book illustrations, reproductions and photographs. It is used by museums and art institutions around the world.</p> <p>Development of the system began in the 1940s and Iconclass was published between 1973 and 1985. It has been available in digital form since the late 1980s, and has been freely accessible online since 2004. Further development is carried out by the Iconclass editorial team in response to input from the community.</p> <p>Since 2024, the ongoing maintenance costs of Iconclass have been refinanced through consortium membership for individuals and institutions. The illustrated sample data and search function are therefore only accessible after registering for a free account. Iconclass Plus also provides consortium members with additional features after registration, including an Iconclass-referenced bibliography on image topics, an AI-based image similarity search, and search links to indexed data offerings.</p>
Web link	<p>Iconclass: https://iconclass.org</p> <p>Finto: https://finto.fi/ic/en/ (Arbeitsstand 2012/2014)</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/iconclass/ (status 2012/2014)</p>
Coverage of entities	Subjects of works/objects
Size (number of concepts)	<p>Iconclass.org: approx. 40.600 (2025-11-22)</p> <p>Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): 39.566 (2025-11-22)</p>
Languages	<p>complete: German, English, French, Portuguese, Japanese, Italian</p> <p>partly available: Finnish, Dutch, Chinese</p>
License	<p>Iconclass.org: database: ODbL v1.0, Data: CC0 1.0 Universal</p> <p>Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): ODbL v1.0</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Henri van de Waal Foundation

	Editorial board: ICONCLASS, Wijngaardenlaan 42, 2252 XP Voorschoten, The Netherlands Hans Brandhorst, Etienne Posthumus
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://iconclass.org/help/about https://github.com/iconclass
Community contributions possible?	Yes, discussion in a forum: https://forum.iconclass.org/ . Editing Iconclass via GitHub: https://iconclass.org/help/data , https://github.com/iconclass/data
Interfaces / Data Transfer	Iconclass.org: FastAPI (https://iconclass.org/help/api), Download: https://github.com/iconclass/data Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): REST API (https://api.finto.fi/ and https://vocabs-api.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/)
Mapping services	Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F459 NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F459 netwerk digitaal erfgoed: https://termennetwerk-api.netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/reconcile/ https://iconclass.org
Available data formats / serialisations	RDF XML, JSON, JSON-LD, JSKOS, Turtle Iconclass AI test set: https://iconclass.org/testset/
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/459 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-23) LOV: not available (2025-11-23) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/iconclass/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190524 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1502787
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, natural history/natural science
Suitable for MDS elements	Classification , Subject keyword
Suitable for additional elements	-

Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	Iconclass.org
	green	Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): reference to Iconclass.org
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and	green	

authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info		
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	red	Iconclass.org: no information on creation or modification dates on the website or in serialisations
	yellow	Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): import and modification date of vocabulary instance on website, not included in serialisations
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	yellow	Vocabulary does not include mappings. Wikidata mapping property 'Iconclass Notation' https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1256 , can be used to create mappings to Iconclass concepts.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	Iconclass.org: no licence information on the website or in serialisations. However, a licence statement for the data can be found in the Github repository https://github.com/iconclass/data/blob/main/LICENSE
	yellow	Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): database licence statement on the vocabulary web page, no information included in concept records or serialisations.

Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Extensive information on the project history on https://iconclass.org/help/about References for the sources of individual concepts are not provided.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	Iconclass.org
	yellow	Finto and Vocabs (DARIAH): publication status outdated. No update since 2014.
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.14 iDAI.chronontology

Brief description	iDAI.chronontology links verbal concepts of time, such as eras, periods and events, with dates. It is primarily used in archaeology and classical studies. All users can access the iDAI.chronontology data, and it is also possible to add your own data by arrangement. The service forms part of iDAI.world and serves as the central gazetteer for time-related concepts within the Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (German Archaeological Institute, DAI). Like iDAI.gazetteer, it is used as an authority file for all time-related information and
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	<p>systems at the DAI, and also links them to global time gazetteer systems.</p> <p>Funded by the German Research Foundation between 2015 and 2018, the project was developed by the DAI and the Institute for Spatial Information and Surveying Technology (i3mainz). The German Archaeological Institute ensures the long-term availability of the data.</p> <p>In the ChronOntology data model, time concepts are Spacetime Volumes (STVs), which have a geographical extension as well as a temporal one. Time concepts with missing or incomplete time or location information are also included, reflecting the current state of research. In addition to temporal and geographical classification, the vocabulary requires an epoch type.</p> <p>This vocabulary is not yet used in portals outside of iDAI.world. However, it is used in research projects.</p>
Web link	https://chronontology.dainst.org/
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, geographical entities (as spatial reference points), periods/eras
Size (number of concepts)	13.843 (2025-11-21)
Languages	German, English
License	CC BY-NC 4.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Deutsches Archäologisches Institut Editorial board: idai.chronontology@dainst.org
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://chronontology.dainst.org/info/about
Community contributions possible?	Reporting of errors, duplicates etc.: idai.chronontology@dainst.org
Interfaces / Data Transfer	REST API (https://chronontology.dainst.org/info/api)
Mapping services	-
Available data formats / serialisations	JSON
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/20473</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-21)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-21)</p> <p>museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/idai-chronontology/</p>

	R:hovono: not available (2025-11-21) Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q93290784	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	-	
Suitable for additional elements	Period/Style	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a	green	

searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	Last modification date in the JSON serialisation, not included in human-readable web presentation. The API allows (machine-readable) access to older versions of the data, see: https://chronontology.dainst.org/info/api
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	yellow	There is no RDF, SKOS or OWL representation. Relationships are modelled, even if the concepts are not represented hierarchically (e.g., 'is part of', 'follows', 'is followed by', 'has other definitions'). A JSON serialisation is available.
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	yellow	SKOS/OWL format not available. The digital provenance is clearly traceable. Qualified relationships are modelled ('is part of', 'follows', 'is followed by' ...).
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	Vocabulary does not include mappings.
The vocabulary is released	yellow	License information stated on vocabulary level,

with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info		but not included in serialisations.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	The digital provenance is clearly traceable. The meta-documentation is also very informative in other respects.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

<h3>3.15 iDAI.gazetteer</h3>	
Brief description	The iDAI.gazetteer, developed by the German Archaeological Institute (DAI), was created to standardise the hierarchical order of location-related information (e.g. places, excavations, historical sites and buildings) held by the DAI. Tags, polygonal

	<p>information and geocoordinates are added on an ongoing basis.</p> <p>The iDAI.gazetteer is used in other DAI information systems, enabling contextualisation with iDAI.objects and iDAI.bibliography.</p> <p>For security reasons, certain content (e.g. coordinates) can only be viewed by registered users.</p> <p>This vocabulary is not yet used in portals outside of iDAI.world. However, it is used in research projects.</p>
Web link	https://gazetteer.dainst.org/app#!/home
Coverage of entities	geographical entities
Size (number of concepts)	143.363 (2025-11-21)
Languages	<p>German, English, Arabic</p> <p>Terms are listed partly in the following languages: English, German, Arabic, Basque, Bulgarian, Chinese, Danish, Finnish, French, Greek, Hebrew, Italian, Japanese, Catalan, Korean, Croatian, Latin, Dutch, Norwegian, Persian, Polish, Portuguese, Russian, Swedish, Serbian, Spanish, Turkish, Ukrainian, Vietnamese</p>
License	CC BY 4.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Publisher: Deutsches Archäologisches Institut (DAI)</p> <p>Editorial board: idai.gazetteer@dainst.de</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://gazetteer.dainst.org/app#!/help
Community contributions possible?	Short descriptions, links to suitable documentation, feedback, corrections and suggestions for additions can be sent by email to idai.gazetteer@dainst.de (ideally including the gazetteer ID).
Interfaces / Data Transfer	REST API (documentation https://gazetteer.dainst.org/app#!/help)
Mapping services	-
Available data formats / serialisations	JSON, KML, RDF XML, GeoJSON, Shapefile
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/1376</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-10-21)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-10-21)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: not available (2025-10-21)</p>

	R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1183375 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q93290690	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Place	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and	green	

constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	red	The vocabulary is currently available as version 2.9.9 (status: 2025-11-22). However, the dates of creation or last modification are not included in the web presentation or the serialisations.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary is released	yellow	License information stated on vocabulary level,

with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info		but not included in serialisations.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Information about the provenance of the concepts is available, but no further details about the maintenance of the gazetteer are given.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.16 iDAI.world Thesaurus

Brief description	The iDAI.world Thesaurus, which was developed between 2015 and 2019, was primarily designed to encompass generic concepts used in the systems of the German Archaeological Institute (DAI). It brings together vocabularies from various fields, including activities, chronologies, geopolitical units, conceptual objects, living beings, materials, natural
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	<p>processes, objects, spatial units, roles (such as military and political offices) and social collective units (such as ethnic groups and groups of people). Its structure corresponds to the Backbone Thesaurus developed within the DARIAH-EU framework. It forms part of the iDAI.Thesauri, which comprise all the historical and current thesauri and vocabularies of the DAI's libraries and projects.</p> <p>As of February 2022, the iDAI.world Thesaurus is also available on the DARIAH-EU Vocabs Service. It is not synchronised with the official DAI offering.</p>
Web link	<p>iDAI.world: http://thesauri.dainst.org/de/concepts/fe65f286.html iDAI.Thesauri: http://thesauri.dainst.org/de.html</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/DAI/</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, corporate bodies, works/objects, geographical entities, periods/eras
Size (number of concepts)	<p>iDAI.world: cannot be determined</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): 6.857 (2025-11-25)</p>
Languages	<p>iDAI.world: German; some terms also translated to: Arabic, Chinese, English, Farsi, French, Italian, Polish, Spanish</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): German, English</p>
License	CC BY 4.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Deutsches Archäologisches Institut</p> <p>Editorial board: http://thesauri.dainst.org/de/about_idai_thesauri.html</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>http://thesauri.dainst.org/de/help.html</p> <p>http://thesauri.dainst.org/de/about_idai_thesauri.html</p>
Ergänzung, Überarbeitung durch Community möglich	Suggestions for additions can be made to the editorial team.
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>iDAI.world: no interface documented</p> <p>Vocabs (DARIAH): REST API (Swagger, https://vocabs-api.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/)</p>
Mapping services	<p>NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F20411</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	iDAI.world: RDF XML, RDF-Turtle, RDF/N-Triples, GeoJSON, KML, Shapefile

	Vocabs (DARIAH): RDF XML, Turtle, JSON-LD	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/20411 FAIRsharing: https://fairsharing.org/FAIRsharing.fee65c LOV: not available (2025-10-14) R:hovono: not available (2025-10-14) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/idai-world/ Wikidata: https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q136706309	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Materials , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	Culture	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	iDAI.world
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	iDAI.world
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	red	iDAI.world: The search function is only available to humans. There is no documented interface or download service.
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	

When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	iDAI.world
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	iDAI.world: versioning only included in serialisations, not in human-readable web presentation.
	yellow	Vocabs (DARIAH): No statement is made regarding any modifications; only the import date is specified (vocabulary level and serialisations).
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	iDAI.world
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for	green	iDAI.world
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH)

vocabularies. (R.1) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	Mappings to other vocabularies not included.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	iDAI.world: licence information stated in human-readable web presentation, but not included in serialisations.
	green	Vocabs (DARIAH): no licence information at concept level, but at vocabulary level and in the vocabulary data record.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	yellow	The iDAI.world thesaurus is suitable for describing archaeological objects at an academic level. However, the lack of definitions and the absence of homonym qualifiers make the vocabulary somewhat difficult to use.
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	The concepts rarely have definitions and are otherwise inadequately described. The meaning of concepts can usually be determined by their hierarchical placement in the thesaurus, although this is not always the case.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	red	The concepts rarely have definitions and are otherwise inadequately described. There are few alternative terms. Homonyms are insufficiently disambiguated. There are neither qualified mappings to other vocabularies nor relevant application examples.

3.17 LIDO Terminology [*LIDO-Terminologie*]

Brief description	<p>The LIDO Terminology supplements the LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects) specification, which is an XML schema for providing metadata for cultural heritage repositories. The aim of LIDO Terminology is to improve the interoperability of object descriptions between different collections. This is achieved by introducing controlled vocabularies for specific elements and attributes within the LIDO XML schema. LIDO Terminology has been developed for elements and attributes for which no suitable controlled vocabulary exists. These are available partly as controlled lists and partly as structured vocabularies.</p> <p>Wherever possible, the definitions of concepts are based on authoritative sources, for instance the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model, Categories for the Description of Works of Art, Art & Architecture Thesaurus, or refers to these.</p>
Web link	<p>ICOM-CIDOC LIDO Working Group http://terminology.lido-schema.org/</p> <p>DANTE: LIDO Event https://dante.gbv.de/#/detail/5eaef032-3421-4c48-8a02-fc626ced923c, Record Type https://dante.gbv.de/#/detail/31f3ffd0-7e48-4404-b12e-b49a0675958b (last update Jan. 2022)</p> <p>VZG Terminology: LIDO Event https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/lido_eventtype/, Record Type (last update 2020); https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/basis_record_type/ (last update 2023)</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts
Size (number of concepts)	<p>digicult xTree.public: 358 (2025-11-23)</p> <p>DANTE, VZG Terminology: 67 (including concepts that are currently being developed and those that have not yet been approved) (2025-11-25)</p>
Languages	Terms: English, German; definitions, notes on use: English
License	<p>digicult xTree.public: CC-BY 4.0</p> <p>DANTE: not specified</p> <p>VZG Terminology: CC-BY-SA 4.0</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Publisher: ICOM Documentation LIDO Working Group</p> <p>Editorial board: LIDO-DE AG (Documentation Committee of the German Museum Association) and ICOM Documentation</p>

	LIDO Working Group
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/lido/lido-oerview/lido-terminology/ https://lido-schema.org/documents/terminology-recommendation.html
Community contributions possible?	Suggestions to the LIDO-DE AG (lido-feedback@sub.uni-goettingen.de), participation in LIDO-DE AG
Interfaces / Data Transfer	digicult xTree.public: SPARQL endpoint (unrestricted access), REST API (restricted access, registration required; documentation: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/docs/xTree_rest_0.86.pdf) DANTE, VZG Terminology: REST API, documentation: https://api.dante.gbv.de/
Mapping services	NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/ (8 sections of the vocabulary)
Available data formats / serialisations	digicult xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON, NT, TriG, Turtle DANTE, VZG Terminology (only LIDO event type, record type): JSKOS, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/20773 , also as 30 individual vocabulary sections: https://bartoc.org/vocabularies?search=lido FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.2d3345 LOV: not available (2025-11-23) museumsvokabular.de: not available (2025-11-23) R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190592 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q132574182
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science, science/technology
Suitable for MDS elements	Event type , Record type Attributes of elements: Object type or designation , Classification , Inventory number , Object description , Materials , Techniques , Measurements , Person/corporate body , Date , Place , Subject keyword , Link to media file , Usage

	rights of media file , Repository of object , Media file: type of media file , Link to published metadata record , Record date	
Suitable for additional elements	Category , Gender Actor , Object Type , Related Work Relationship Type , @Pref Attributes of elements: Identifier , Nationality Actor , Gender Actor , Period/Style , Event Description Set , Vital Place Actor	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek , Collections from Colonial Contexts , museum-digital	
Comments	Introduction: https://docs.nfdi4culture.de/lido-schulung/modul-kontrolliertes-vokabular	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3)	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology

more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	Vocabulary is also ISO 25964 compliant.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	red	DANTE: mappings not included
	red	VZG Terminology: mappings not included. Instead, under 'Mapping ' there is a reference to the URI at digiCULT xTree.public.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable.	green	digiCULT xTree.public, DANTE, VZG Terminology: licence information human-readable on vocabulary level, also included in all serialisations

(R.1.1) more info		
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	digicult xTree.public: available provenance information (e.g. source references) is not displayed in full in the data or integrated into the serialisations
	yellow	DANTE, VZG Terminology: see digicult xTree.public. The service also publishes concepts that are currently being developed or that have not yet been approved (example: LIDO event type Looting)
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	yellow	DANTE, VZG Terminology: The service also publishes concepts that are currently being developed or that have not yet been approved. Publication status outdated; both available vocabulary sections have been significantly expanded since the last update (2020/2023).
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	yellow	DANTE, VZG Terminology: hierarchical structure of the vocabulary has not been adapted, meaning of concepts therefore unclear publication status outdated, so newer concepts and definitions are not included
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	yellow	DANTE, VZG Terminology: hierarchical structure of the vocabulary has not been adapted publication status outdated, so newer concepts, definitions, and application examples are not included

3.18 Furniture Classification [*Möbeltypologie*]

Brief description	<p>The Furniture Classification (Möbeltypologie) contains object designations based on function and form for domestic furniture in German-speaking countries. It is divided into seven basic types and 42 form types.</p> <p>This vocabulary was developed from a sub-area of the Object Naming File (OBG) and continues to be expanded and maintained there: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://obg.vocnet.org/&startNode=00000793 (separate area in digiCULT xTree.public) and http://obg.vocnet.org/00000793 (as sub-section of OBG). In 2005, however, it was presented as a separate illustrated publication containing around 700 concepts: Gitta Böth: Möbel. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen. Munich and Berlin 2005.</p> <p>The contents of this print version of the Furniture Classification were also adopted by the museum-digital md:term terminology service. The concepts available at museum-digital differ from the official OBG version in scope and content.</p> <p>The Furniture Classification is also available on museumsvokabular.de as a PDF, RDF or XML download, or as an experimental SkoHub implementation. This offering is based on data extracted in 2006 and has not undergone any further editorial development.</p>
Web link	<p>Furniture Classification as part of the Object Naming File (OBG), digiCULT xTree.public: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://obg.vocnet.org/&startNode=00000793</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/moebeltypologie/ SkoHub: https://museumsvokabular-de.github.io/Museumsvokabular-Hub/moebel.html</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/ and https://term.museum-digital.de/moebel/tag/1</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: 305 (2025-11-13)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: 422 (all serialisations, including PDF, SkoHub, 2025-11-13)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: 350 (all serialisations, 2025-11-13)</p>
Languages	German

License	Object Naming File: CC BY 4.0 museumsvokabular.de: CC BY-NC-SA 2.0 DE museum-digital md:term: not specified
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher/Editorial board: Westfälisches Museumsamt / Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern
Editorial team active?	Active development in digiCULT xTree.public, as part of the Object Naming File (OBG) (see chapter on Object Naming File) museum-digital md:term, museumsvokabular.de: no editorial activity
Web link documentation	http://www.museumsvokabular.de/sites/museumsvokabular/files/vocabulary/downloads/systematik-moebel.pdf (abbreviated introduction of the printed publication)
Community contributions possible?	Object Naming File, furniture section: Suggestions for revision can be sent to the Landesstelle für nichtstaatliche Museen in Bayern. No options for additions or revision in museum-digital md:term and museumsvokabular.de
Interfaces / Data Transfer	digiCULT xTree.public: REST API (exclusively for institutions within the cooperative); https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/docs/xTree_rest_0.86.pdf . RDF dumps of the entire Object Naming File are made available. museumsvokabular.de: download option: https://museumsvokabular.de/objektbezeichnungsdatei-obg/ and SkoHub: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub museum-digital md:term: REST API (documentation: https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)
Mapping services	Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/moebel/reconciliation/tag?lang=de
Available data formats / serialisations	digiCULT xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON museumsvokabular.de: RDF XML, museumdat XML; SkoHub: JSON. Turtle is also available on the GitHub page: https://github.com/museumsvokabular-de/Museumsvokabular-Hub . However, this is not an official museumsvokabular.de service. museum-digital md:term: RDF XML, JSON-LD
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/487

	FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-13) LOV: not available (2025-11-13) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/moebeltypologie/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190546 Wikidata: https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q136705996	
Suitable for field of specialisation	History, cultural history, art history	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	-	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
		<i>museumsvocabular.de: The SkoHub implementation is not yet included in the standard service offer. Therefore, it is not included in the FAIRness assessment.</i>
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvocabular.de: In the standard service, it is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. This is only possible in the experimental SkoHub implementation. Otherwise, it can only be addressed indirectly via either entries in Wikidata or the registries.
	green	museum-digital md:term
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvocabular.de: Each concept in the available download files has an identifier. However, this identifier does not have the form of a URL and cannot be supplemented to a regular URI using a base URL. Example: moebel/00000793.

	green	museum-digital md:term
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: REST API (exclusively for institutions within the cooperative); RDF dumps of the entire Object Naming File are made available, though not of the furniture section.
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: A search for terms is only possible indirectly in the download files. The experimental SkoHub implementation allows you to search for terms and concepts.
	green	museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: Download formats do not include identifiers in the form of URIs; only a human-readable representation is returned. A machine-readable representation is available via the SkoHub implementation.
	green	museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: The vocabulary is indexed in Wikidata and in registries. Concepts and terms are not indexed individually in the standard service. However, individual terms can be searched for using the SkoHub implementation.
	green	museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over	green	digiCULT xTree.public

time. (A.2) more info	green	museumsvokabular.de
	green	museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museumsvokabular.de: There is no versioning. While the creation date of the data record is included in the RDF serialisation, there is no modification date. Therefore, it can be assumed that the offer has not been updated since it was made available.
	green	museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museumsvokabular.de
	green	museum-digital md:term
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	No mappings available. There is also no corresponding Wikidata mapping property.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: The licence information is included in the RDF XML serialisation only, not in the human-readable presentation of the vocabulary.
	green	museumsvokabular.de
	red	museum-digital md:term: no licence information, also not in the available serialisations
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts,	red	museumsvokabular.de: The PDF version of the print publication does contain bibliographic information. However, this only reflects the

<p>including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>		<p>status quo at the time it was created.</p> <p>For the digital conversions, there is insufficient documentation on the origin and development of the vocabulary. Any discrepancies from the terminology used in the print publication are not documented.</p> <p>Concepts and terms marked as 'deprecated' are included in the PDF, as well as in the RDF and XML files available for download and via SkoHub (example: https://museumsvokabular-de.github.io/Museumsvokabular-Hub/moebel/00002461.json).</p>
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>Synonyms are available throughout. However, application examples, usage notes and qualified mappings are lacking.</p>

3.19 museum-digital Vocabularies (md:term)

<p>Brief description</p>	<p>To ensure interoperability between the datasets generated by numerous museums and collections on its web portal, museum-digital offers its own md:term vocabularies for the most important search entries, namely 'Persons and</p>
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	<p>Corporate Bodies', 'Geography and Buildings', 'Keywords' and 'Time Terms'. These are curated by a central editorial team. The md:term terminology service also offers additional German-language vocabularies, such as the Nomenclature for Inventorying Cultural History Collections in Museums, Object Naming File and Furniture Classification.</p> <p>With regard to content, only the md:term vocabularies are actively developed by museum-digital.</p> <p>Through their use in at least one cataloguing instance in museum-digital, new concepts and terms are automatically added to the offering and undergo the editorial process, which involves actively amending the collection's object data. These vocabularies are made available in machine-readable formats for external reuse. All the vocabularies except 'Time Terms' contain a large number of mappings to GND, Wikidata, GeoNames, etc.</p> <p>The vocabulary 'Persons and Corporate Bodies' comprises of records of individual persons and corporate bodies as well as ethnic groups, which are subject of a work or participated in an event in the object's history.</p> <p>In addition to the preferred names, the 'Geography and Buildings' vocabulary includes geographical coordinates. Each geographical entity is assigned to a specific location type, such as 'buildings ', 'streets ', 'towns ', 'bodies of water ' or 'mountains '. Locations are also included under their historical names. While a structured reference to a location under its current name is not always available, it can be derived from the comprehensive mappings provided.</p> <p>The 'Keywords' vocabulary primarily comprises generic concepts for describing and contextualising collection objects. Some of these are classified hierarchically and provided with short descriptions from a variety of sources, often including Wikipedia, and are linked to external authority data.</p> <p>The term 'Time Terms' essentially refers to numerical data for dates and time periods. While time information is normalised according to specific editorial rules, they are not aligned in accordance with ISO 8601 — the international standard for numerical date formats and time specifications. However, the ISO standard is taken into account in exports. Verbal expressions such as 'early 19th century' are converted into specific time periods. (See the guidelines: https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info/Grundkonzepte/Zeiten.html) Concepts relating to a specific subject or epoch (e.g. 'Baroque', 'Meiji period') are not part of this vocabulary, but are included in the 'Keywords' vocabulary.</p>
Web link	https://term.museum-digital.de/
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works, persons, corporate bodies, geographical entities

Size (number of concepts)	328.182 persons and corporate bodies, ethnic groups 123.644 geographical entities (including buildings) 180.767 keywords (including epochs) 155.631 time terms (2025-11-13)
Languages	German, English, Russian, Ukrainian, Hungarian; preferred terms and short descriptions partly available in other languages
License	No licence information In the BARTOC registry, copyright protection is stated. The source of this information could not be determined.
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher/Editorial board: museum-digital
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info/Grundkonzepte/Normdaten.html The vocabulary management tool nodac and the editorial team's working methods are documented here: https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info/nodac/index.html
Community contributions possible?	Cataloguers working with the museum-digital database musdb may suggest new concepts. Only editors with access to the nodac vocabulary module can modify authority data (see https://de.handbook.museum-digital.info/Grundkonzepte/Normdaten.html).
Interfaces / Data Transfer	REST API (documentation: https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)
Mapping services	Reconciliation API (documentation): https://blog.museum-digital.org/2024/07/03/reconciliation-apis-arrive-to-museum-digital/ Time terms: https://term.museum-digital.de/md-de/reconciliation/time?lang=de Keywords: https://term.museum-digital.de/md-de/reconciliation/tag?lang=de Geographical entities, buildings: https://term.museum-digital.de/md-de/reconciliation/place?lang=de Persons and corporate bodies: https://term.museum-digital.de/md-de/reconciliation/actor?lang=de

Available data formats / serialisations	RDF XML, JSON-LD	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/20519 (keywords), https://bartoc.org/en/node/20518 (time terms), https://bartoc.org/en/node/20517 (geographical entities), https://bartoc.org/en/node/20516 (persons and corporate bodies)</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-14-11)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-14-11)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/mdterm-vokabularbrowser/</p> <p>R:hovono: not available (2025-14-11)</p> <p>Wikidata: Keywords: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126950973, geographical entities: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126950927, time terms: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126950978, persons and corporate bodies: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126950961</p>	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Suitable for use across disciplines, e.g., for archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science, science/technology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Person/corporate body , Place , Subject keyword , Rights holder of media file , Repository of object , Institution providing record	
Suitable for additional elements	Display Date , Period/Style	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	museum-digital	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	yellow	The vocabulary or its four parts cannot be addressed directly with a unique identifier. However, they can be addressed indirectly via either entries in Wikidata or the registry BARTOC.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1)	green	

more info		
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	yellow	Data records of unverified concepts are also made available for download. It is unclear whether the URI will be redirected in the event of subsequent deletion.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably	green	

machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info		
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	red	Licence information is not provided. The origin of the licence statement specified in BARTOC remains unclear.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	The manual and the accompanying YouTube videos explain in detail the importance of authority data and editorial work with the vocabulary management tool nodac. However, the general rules for maintaining the vocabulary are not as clearly explained. For example, the editorial team does not detail how it handles the inevitable error rates of semi-automated vocabulary maintenance. This would include information on the human checks and optimisations carried out, the procedures used and the intervals at which reconciliations take place, as well as an explanation of why certain error rates are considered acceptable.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to	yellow	Sometimes definitions are missing. The brief

help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info		descriptions are usually taken from Wikipedia, but it is unclear how thoroughly they have been reviewed. Regarding the generic concepts, their hierarchical arrangement within the vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	Although some concepts lack definitions, sufficient attributes are usually provided to enable understanding. However, the hierarchical order of the keywords is inconsistent in places and does not cover the entire vocabulary section. The high density of mappings to other important vocabularies is particularly noteworthy. In the keywords section, the vocabulary excels at displaying relevant example objects from museum-digital.

<h3>3.20 nomisma</h3>	
Brief description	<p>nomisma.org is an international, collaborative project that aims to provide stable digital representations of numismatic concepts, based on the principles of Linked Open Data. The project consists of a controlled vocabulary, an ontology, and a data model for classifying and structuring numismatic concepts.</p> <p>The number of actively involved persons is relatively small, with some individuals active in both the working groups and the steering committee.</p> <p>Identifiers are created on a country-specific basis, but in some cases generic concepts must be created to allow identifiers to be used across national borders. Modelling is generally based on locations rather than mints, even though mints in the same location can differ significantly across different eras (e.g. the Republican and Imperial mints in Rome).</p> <p>Nomisma is particularly used in specialist numismatic portals (ikmk.net, MANTIS, numishare-based type portals like for instance Online Coins of Ostrogothic Italy (OCOI), Coinage of the Roman Republic Online (CRRO), Online Coins of the Roman Empire (OCRE), Coinage of the Macedonian Kings of the Argead Dynasty (Pella), Coin Hoards of the Roman Republic, Corpus Nummorum Online, Nomismata Byzantion and others.</p>
Web link	http://nomisma.org/
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, persons, corporate bodies, geographical

	entities, works/objects, materials, periods
Size (number of concepts)	12.874 (2025-11-17)
Languages	English; additional languages for preferred terms, these are extracted from Wikidata
License	CC BY 3.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	American Numismatic Society Editorial board: steering committee; various working groups provide suggestions: https://nomisma.org/about/working_groups/
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	Ontology: https://nomisma.org/ontology Cookbook: https://nomisma.hypotheses.org/category/nomisma-org-cookbook
Community contributions possible?	No, but you can contact the working group. The editors are listed alongside their email addresses, ORCID IDs and nomisma IDs. See https://nomisma.org/documentation/contribute/
Interfaces / Data Transfer	SPARQL endpoint, REST API: http://nomisma.org/data/ ATOM feed interface: https://nomisma.org/feed/
Mapping services	Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1822 NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1822 OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://nomisma.org/apis/reconcile
Available data formats / serialisations	RDF XML, JSON-LD, RDF-Turtle
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/1822 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-17) LOV: not available (2025-11-17) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/normdatenportal-ndp/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1194785

	Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q24578999	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, history, numismatics, classical archaeology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification (nominal), Materials , Techniques , Person/corporate body , Place , Subject keyword , Repository of object , Institution providing record	
Suitable for additional elements	Inscriptions/Marks (Monogramme)	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	museum-digital	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a	green	

searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	Versioning is only included in the machine-readable serialisations, not the web display.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	Mappings included. Wikidata mapping property 'nomisma ID': https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P2950
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is	yellow	License information stated on vocabulary level, but not for the individual concepts. The licence is not included in the

preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info		machine-readable serialisations.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	The definitions are kept very brief to suit the target audience; more detailed explanations would sometimes be helpful for users from other fields.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	A large number of attributes are provided for each concept. In particular, these include mappings to other vocabularies and synonyms (under 'Alternate Label'), geographical coordinates for mints, as well as role and biographical information for persons. Examples of use are provided in the form of links to coin types from specialist vocabularies.

3.21 Authority File Portal of the Münzkabinett Berlin [Normdatenportal des Münzkabinetts Berlin]

Brief description	The Authority File Portal of the Münzkabinett Berlin offers numismatic designations and terminology in an online, searchable interface. Data can also be downloaded. The portal contains concepts relevant to coin cataloguing. The Münzkabinett thus fulfils its obligation of promoting numismatic research, particularly in the areas of digitisation
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	<p>and the use of Linked Open Data (LOD), and provides its partners and the scientific community with the necessary tools.</p> <p>The vocabulary is also available on the DANTE vocabulary platform. Here, the number of categories listed as individual vocabularies and the number of concepts differ.</p> <p>The vocabulary is intended for the scientific community, particularly institutions using the ikmk.net service. For reuse in KENOM, permalinks are adapted accordingly.</p>
Web link	<p>https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp</p> <p>DANTE: https://dante.gbv.de/ (incomplete: 14 vocabulary sections, 5 categories are missing)</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, persons, corporate bodies, geographical entities, periods/eras
Size (number of concepts)	<p>Authority File Portal: 23.576 (2025-11-17)</p> <p>DANTE: 15.532 (2025-11-19)</p>
Languages	German, English
License	<p>Authority File Portal: CC BY 4.0</p> <p>DANTE: CC BY-NC-SA 4.0</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Münzkabinett, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Stiftung Preußischer Kulturbesitz
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Separate documentation not available.</p> <p>Description of data elements in the Münzkabinett Berlin Online Catalogue (IKMK):</p> <p>https://ikmk.smb.museum/eMuseum?lang=de&exhibition_id=88</p>
Community contributions possible?	No, but comments and corrections from users can be sent to the editorial team by email.
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>REST API and download service in various data formats: https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/category (without detailed documentation)</p> <p>External services: REST API in DANTE (documentation: https://api.dante.gbv.de/start/)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: CSV download</p>
Mapping services	
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>RDF XML, JSON-LD, RDF-Turtle, RDF-NT</p> <p>DANTE: JSKOS, MARC-XML, MARC-JSON, Turtle, N-Triples</p>

Reference in registries / Wikidata	BAROC: https://bartoc.org/vocabularies?search=ikmk (15 individual vocabulary sections, listed as IKMK vocabularies) FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-17) LOV: not available (2025-11-17) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/normdatenportal-ndp/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190556 Wikidata: https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q136705983	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, history, numismatics, classical archaeology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification (nominal), Materials , Techniques , Person/corporate body , Place , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	Period/Style	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	

When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE

The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	Authority File Portal
	green	DANTE: Only some of the mappings available in the Authority File Portal are also available here (in particular to nomisma.org and GeoNames).
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	Authority File Portal: The licence is specified in human-readable form at vocabulary level, but is not shown for individual concepts. Moreover, it is not included in the serialisations in machine-readable form.
	green	DANTE
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Authority File Portal: Although the data elements in IKMK are explained in detail, there is no similarly detailed documentation for the Authority File Portal. Important meta information is provided in external sources (e.g., in the News item on the launch of NDP on 19 July 2019 and in the news item on the launch of the API on 19 June 2024), both linked in the About us section on the page https://ikmk.smb.museum/ndp/about?lang=en . The API and download options are easy to find, but detailed interface documentation is lacking.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	Authority File Portal: In some cases, definitions are omitted because certain concepts are considered self-explanatory within the specialist community. Outside this community, however, they are not necessarily intuitive. Often, however, the meaning of the concepts can be deduced from cross-references, geo-coordinates and/or web links.
	red	DANTE: no definitions available
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant	yellow	Authority File Portal: The categories are clearly defined. However, concepts are only defined where deemed necessary. Some relevant attributes are provided (in particular mappings

attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info		to other vocabularies, language variants, further web links where applicable, standard-compliant currency codes, etc.). However, additional attributes would sometimes be useful (e.g. application examples).
	yellow	DANTE: Only certain attributes are available, e.g., terms/alternative terms and selected mappings – in particular to nomisma.org and GeoNames. Above all, definitions are lacking. However, the map representations of locations are a welcome addition. A distinction is also made between the mint and the place of discovery.

3.22 Object Naming File [*Objektbezeichnungsdatei, OBG*]

Brief description	<p>The Object Naming File (Objektbezeichnungsdatei, OBG) is a thesaurus-like, polyhierarchical compilation of object types and categories used for cataloguing objects in museums and collections. Entries (object designations) have been compiled since the 1980s from around 150 German museums. Since 2008, a Germany-wide editorial group has been revising, continuing and publishing the Object Naming File (formerly 'Oberbegriffsdatei') in the vocabulary management system digiCULT xTree.public. Specialist groups edit individual subject areas.</p> <p>The OBG is also available under the name 'Oberbegriffsdatei' via museum-digital's terminology service md:term, and on the DANTE vocabulary platform. An RDF download is available at museumsvocabular.de. However, all these instances differ in scope and content from the official version of the OBG.</p> <p>The terminology for individual subject areas has also been published separately:</p> <p>Callweys Handbuch der Uhrentypen. Von der Armbanduhr bis zum Zappler. Munich 1994, reprint 2022</p> <p>Gefäße und Formen. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen, Munich 1996</p> <p>Möbel. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen, Munich 2005</p> <p>Kopfbedeckungen. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen, Munich 2013</p> <p>Werkzeuge. Eine Typologie für Museen und Sammlungen. Teil 1: Axt – Feile, Raspel, Schaber – Hacke, Haken, Harke.</p>
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	<p>Haue, Berlin/Munich 2020</p> <p>Although parts of the OBG are available online, these differ in scope and content from the official version. A detailed description can be found in the relevant sections Typology of Vessels, General Classification for Museums, Furniture Classification</p>
Web link	<p>Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern: https://objektbezeichnungsdatei.de</p> <p>digiCULT xTree.public: http://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http%3A//obg.vocnet.org/&startNode=obg00651&lang=de&d=n</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/ (under its former name Oberbegriffsdatei)</p> <p>DANTE: https://dante.gbv.de/</p> <p>VZG Terminology: https://uri.gbv.de/terminology/objektbezeichnungsdatei/</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: 7.688 (2025-11-19)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: 7.730 (2025-11-19)</p> <p>DANTE: 7.359 (2025-11-19)</p>
Languages	German
License	<p>OBG in digiCULT xTree.public: CC BY 4.0</p> <p>DANTE, VZG Terminology: CC BY-SA 4.0</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: not specified</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/objektbezeichnungsdatei-obg/ : CC BY SA - without version number</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>Publisher: Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern</p> <p>Editorial board: Working group consisting of digiCULT-Verbund eG, Institut für Museumsforschung, Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Preußischer Kulturbesitz, Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern and Museum der Arbeit, Stiftung Historische Museen Hamburg as well as independent members. The working group is part of the Documentation Section of the German Museum Association (https://www.museumsbund.de/fachgruppe-dokumentation/arb-eitsgruppen/). Members of the editorial team are named here: https://museumsberatung-bayern.de/inventarisierung/obg</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	http://www.museumsvokabular.de/sites/museumsvokabular/fil

	<p>es/vocabulary/downloads/OBG%20Beschreibung-20220512.pdf</p> <p>See also https://museumsberatung-bayern.de/inventarisierung/obg</p>
Community contributions possible?	<p>Suggestions for revisions can be sent to the editorial team or the Landesstelle für die nichtstaatlichen Museen in Bayern. An email address is provided here: https://museumsberatung-bayern.de/inventarisierung/obg.</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>digicult xTree.public: REST API (restricted access, registration required, https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/docs/xTree_rest_0.86.pdf)</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: REST API (documentation: https://term.museum-digital.de/swagger/)</p> <p>DANTE: REST API (documentation: https://api.dante.gbv.de/start/)</p>
Mapping services	<p>Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/oberbegriffsdatei/reconciliation/tag?lang=de</p> <p>OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://term.museum-digital.de/oberbegriffsdatei/reconciliation/tag?lang=de</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>digicult xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: RDF XML, JSON-LD</p> <p>DANTE: JSKOS, MARC-XML, MARC-JSON, Turtle, N-Triples</p> <p>VZG-Terminology: JSKOS, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples</p>
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/505</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-19)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/objektbezeichnungsdatei-obg/</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190598</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q57978535</p>
Suitable for field of specialisation	European ethnology, history, cultural history, art history, applied art
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword
Suitable for additional	-

elements		
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)		Europeana , museum-digital
Comments		-
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: It is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. However, it can be addressed indirectly via either Wikidata or registry entries.
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	yellow	digicult xTree.public: REST API (exclusively for institutions within the cooperative); RDF dumps of the OBG are made available.
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	digicult xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE

	green	VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museum-digital md:term
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and	green	digiCULT xTree.public: Linking to other

<p>constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>		vocabularies is under development and will be expanded further. Current status: GND mapping (650 concepts), AAT mapping (66 concepts) and Wikidata mapping (16 concepts)
	green	museum-digital md:term: see comment for digiCULT xTree.public
	red	DANTE: mapping properties have not been included
	red	VZG Terminology: mapping properties have not been included
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: The licence information is included in the RDF XML serialisation only, not in the human-readable presentation of the vocabulary.
	red	museum-digital md:term: no licence information, also not in the available serialisations
	green	DANTE
	green	VZG Terminology: In the serialisations, the licence is specified only in the data record for the vocabulary itself, not for individual concepts.
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	yellow	Essential metadata is either missing or can only be found with considerable effort. This includes information about the creation and maintenance of the vocabulary. The licence is not specified in the vocabulary's metadata documentation.
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	green	
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	green	digiCULT xTree.public: No definitions are available for many concepts. However, their position in the vocabulary hierarchy provides a good orientation for understanding their meaning.
	green	museum-digital md:term: see digiCULT xTree.public

	red	DANTE: Definitions are not included. However, the position of concepts in the hierarchy provides some guidance.
	yellow	VZG Terminology: Definitions are not included. However, the position of concepts in the hierarchy provides some guidance.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Some relevant attributes, such as synonyms, are available. Definitions are often missing. Application examples and cross-references are not available.

<h3>3.23 Pleiades</h3>	
Brief description	Pleiades is a gazetteer and graph of the historical geography of the ancient world, focusing on the ancient Mediterranean region. It was created by specialists in the field. The database is gradually being expanded to include additional cultural areas, both in terms of space and time. Information is provided in both human- and machine-readable formats.
Web link	http://pleiades.stoa.org/
Coverage of entities	geographical entities
Size (number of concepts)	41.685 (2025-07-21)
Languages	English
License	CC BY 3.0 US
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW), New York University and Ancient World Mapping Center (AWMC), University of North Carolina. Editorial board: Editorial College
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://pleiades.stoa.org/docs https://pleiades.stoa.org/downloads

	https://github.com/isawnyu/pleiades-gazetteer	
Community contributions possible?	Yes, after registration. All registered users can suggest changes and additions. Content is also developed by a large number of individually credited volunteer contributors: https://pleiades.stoa.org/participate	
Interfaces / Data Transfer	REST API	
Mapping services	https://geocollider-sinatra.herokuapp.com/reconcile	
Available data formats / serialisations	RDF XML, JSON, CSV, KML, TURTLE, ATOM	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/20431</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-30)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-30)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: not available (2025-11-30)</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1752884</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q24423804</p>	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, classical archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history	
Suitable for MDS elements	Place , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	Repository/Location (previous location)	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess-ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a	green	

vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info		
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	Datasets are archived periodically, with the respective status made available on GitHub.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML	green	

with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info		
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	Since 2025, there has been a Linked Data Sidebar containing links to other vocabularies, such as nomisma and Wikidata. URIs have also been integrated into the JSON dataset. https://pleiades.stoa.org/help/using-pleiades-data/linked-data-sidebar
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	The licence information is not included in all serialisations of the data.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	There is hardly any further information available on lesser-known places. The information on individual places is highly selective and depends on contributors' choices. ⁹ Some place characteristics are very vague and cryptic, e.g., 'an ancient place' with unclear source references.

⁹ Weiland, J. (2021). Review: Pleiades. *Society for Classical Studies*.
<https://classicalstudies.org/scs-blog/jon-weiland/review-pleiades> (last accessed 2025-12-05)

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
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<h3>3.24 Thesaurus of the Vienna Museum of Science and Technology [<i>Technikthesaurus – Thesaurus des Technischen Museums Wien, TMW</i>]</h3>	
<p>Brief description</p>	<p>A polyhierarchically structured thesaurus for indexing objects in collections of technical history.</p> <p>Developed by the Vienna Museum of Science and Technology (TMW) from around 2012 onwards, the thesaurus was created for the cataloguing and indexing of its collection. The aim was to improve the findability of its own holdings in web databases.</p> <p>The vocabulary provides generic concepts for describing and subject indexing museum objects. These include object designations, as well as, in the 'Aspekt' facet, concepts for classification according to operating mode, manufacturing method, processes, systematics, functional characteristics and material properties. In addition, there are facets for 'Brand Names' and 'Epochs'. The 'Concepts' facet enables higher-level thematic contextualisation.</p> <p>The thesaurus is structured in accordance with DIN 1463-1 (ISO 2788).</p> <p>The vocabulary is also available via the museum-digital md:term website. These two offerings are not synchronised. The URIs of the concepts have not been synchronised or mapped to each other either.</p>
<p>Web link</p>	<p>TMW: https://data.tmw.at/thesaurus/42362</p> <p>term-based search: https://data.tmw.at/term</p> <p>museum-digital md:term: https://term.museum-digital.de/</p>
<p>Coverage of entities</p>	<p>Generic concepts for objects/works, persons</p>

Size (number of concepts)	TMW: 40.061 (among them 11.018 geographical entities and 5.324 concept candidates; 2025-11-26) museum-digital md:term: 7.686 (2025-11-26)
Languages	German
License	TMW: CC0 1.0 museum-digital md:term: not specified
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher and editorial board: Vienna Museum of Science and Technology
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	Motivation, structure, content: https://museumsdokumente.de/fg_doku/archiv-Veranstaltungen/2013_Oktober/20131016-Winkler.pdf
Community contributions possible?	not specified
Interfaces / Data Transfer	TMW: OpenAPI https://data.tmw.at/ ; no download service museum-digital md:term download service: https://term.museum-digital.de/downloads
Mapping services	https://term.museum-digital.de/technikthesaurus/reconciliation/tag?lang=de
Available data formats / serialisations	Both services: RDF XML, JSON
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/20462 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-26) LOV: not available (2025-11-26) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/thesaurus-des-technischen-museums-wien/ R:hovono: not available (2025-11-26) Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q126952454
Suitable for field of specialisation	History, cultural history, history of science and technology
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Subject keyword , Classification , Person/corporate body , Place
Suitable for additional elements	Period/Style
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-

Comments	The TMW also offers a JSON serialisation, although it is not documented. Example: https://data.tmw.at/thesaurus/35149/json	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	TMW
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: It is not possible to address the vocabulary directly with a unique identifier. However, it can be addressed indirectly via either Wikidata or the BARTOC entries.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term

communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info		
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	TMW: last modification date not included in the web presentation, but in the serialisations
	green	museum-digital md:term: last modification date is included in the web presentation and the JSON format
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	TMW, museum-digital md:term
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	TMW: Mappings to GND and Wikidata are partly available, also references to Wikipedia are included.
	red	museum-digital md:term: The mappings of the TMW version are not included. There is no corresponding Wikidata mapping property.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	TMW: licence statement with URI is included in the serialisations

	yellow	museum-digital md:term: no explicit indication of a licence, no inclusion in the serialisations provided
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	TMW: information on the creation of the vocabulary is only available in the form of a presentation by a TMW staff member from 2013
	red	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	Definitions are frequently missing (museum-digital md:term: available in 946 of 7686 data records). The hierarchical arrangement of concepts within a vocabulary helps to clarify contextualisation.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	TMW: definitions are frequently missing, no alternative terms and application examples; mappings available
	yellow	museum-digital md:term: definitions are frequently missing, no alternative terms and application examples. The mappings of the TMW version are not included.

3.25 Trachsler – Classification of Cultural-Historical Material Objects [*Trachsler – Systematik kulturhistorischer Sachgüter*]

<p>Brief description</p>	<p>The 'Trachsler' classification system, developed by Walter Trachsler, is used to structure and organise cultural heritage objects. Created on behalf of the Verband der Museen der Schweiz (Swiss Museums Association), it was first published in 1981 in book form under the title <i>Systematik kulturhistorischer Sachgüter. Eine Klassifikation nach Funktionsgruppen zum Gebrauch in Museen und Sammlungen</i>.</p> <p>In its current form, the thesaurus comprises almost 5,000 concepts. It is edited by the Verband der Museen der Schweiz and is available via museums.ch. From there, the current version can be accessed in digiCULT xTree.public.</p> <p>The vocabulary is also available in various PDF versions, each of which differs in content:</p> <p>Vereinigung der Walliser Museen (Association of Valais Museums): https://musees-vs.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Systematik2000V02.pdf</p> <p>Museenland Graubünden (Museums of Grisons): https://www.museenland-gr.ch/fileadmin/user_upload/Museen_Graubunden_Material/20-Vorherige-Webseite/Dokumente/Fachpapiere/Trachsler_Systematik.pdf</p> <p>Any deviations from these PDF versions are not addressed in the offerings on digiCULT, xTree.public or museums.ch. The offerings are not synchronised.</p>
<p>Web link</p>	<p>Instance at digiCULT xTree.public: https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://digicult.vocnet.org/trachsler/&startNode=t04884&lang=de&d=n</p> <p>museums.ch: https://www.museums.ch/de/fachwelt/fachthemen/inventar-1159.html</p>
<p>Coverage of entities</p>	<p>Generic concepts for objects/works</p>
<p>Size (number of concepts)</p>	<p>museums.ch: 4.876 (2025-11-19) digiCULT xTree.public: 4.876 (2025-11-19)</p>
<p>Languages</p>	<p>German, French, Italian</p>
<p>License</p>	<p>Information in external sources only</p>
<p>Publisher / Editorial</p>	<p>museums.ch: VMS (Verband der Museen der Schweiz). The</p>

responsibility	vocabulary is maintained in digiCULT xTree.public.
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	<p>Structure, content: https://musees-vs.ch/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Systematik2000V02.pdf</p> <p>Very short documentation in https://www.museums.ch/de/fachwelt/fachthemen/inventar-1159.html, no documentation available in digiCULT xTree.public</p> <p>Landesstelle für Museen Baden-Württemberg: https://www.landesstelle.de/fileadmin/Daten/Downloads/Unterlagen_Handreichungen/Systematisierung.pdf</p>
Community contributions possible?	museums.ch: Suggestions can be sent via email.
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>digiCULT xTree.public: restricted access REST API. Unlike other xTree vocabularies, the RDF dumps are not made available for download.</p> <p>museums.ch: download: https://www.museums.ch/de/fachwelt/fachthemen/inventar-1159.html</p>
Mapping services	-
Available data formats / serialisations	<p>museums.ch: CSV, XML</p> <p>digiCULT xTree.public: RDF XML, JSON (only via restricted access API)</p>
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: not available (2025-08-22)</p> <p>FAIRsharing: not available (2025-08-22)</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-08-22)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: not available (2025-08-22)</p> <p>R:hovono: not available (2025-08-22)</p> <p>Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q137259639</p>
Suitable for field of specialisation	History, cultural history, art
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Subject keyword
Suitable for additional elements	-
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-
Comments	-

FAIRness		
	Assess- ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	green	museums.ch: link to digiCULT xTree.public service
	yellow	Valais museums: not directly addressable, but a Wikidata entry exists
	yellow	Museums of Grisons: not directly addressable, but a Wikidata entry exists
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public
	yellow	museums.ch: only simple IDs without URL formatting are available in XML and CSV. However, the digiCULT xTree.public URIs are included in the XML format as source IDs.
	yellow	Valais museums: human-readable identifiers in a PDF that do not meet the criterion of global uniqueness.
	yellow	Museums of Grisons: human-readable identifiers in a PDF that do not meet the criterion of global uniqueness
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: only searchable for humans, restricted access API
	yellow	museums.ch: see digiCULT xTree.public. Additionally, there is a download service for CSV and XML formats.
	red	Valais museums: only searchable for humans. Concepts are only available in the unstructured data format PDF.
	red	Museums of Grisons: only searchable for humans. Concepts are only available in the unstructured data format PDF.
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	

<p>When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: The URI for the individual concepts does not redirect to the website, but produces an error message instead. The other formats cannot be dereferenced without an open interface and precise knowledge of the required syntax modifications.
	yellow	museums.ch: see digiCULT xTree.public
	red	Valais museums: Concepts are only available in the unstructured data format PDF.
	red	Museums of Grisons: Concepts are only available in the unstructured data format PDF.
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: Although the vocabulary is accessible via a link on the museums.ch website, it is not listed on the xTree.public landing page or under the 'Vocabularies' menu item. However, concepts are indexed separately.
	yellow	museums.ch: The vocabulary is directly findable via search engines. Concepts are indexed separately in digiCULT xTree.public.
	yellow	Valais museums: The vocabulary is findable via search engines, but concepts are not indexed separately.
	yellow	Museums of Grisons: The vocabulary is findable via search engines, but concepts are not indexed separately.
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info</p>	green	
<p>Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info</p>	green	museums.ch, digiCULT xTree.public
	green	Valais museums
	green	Museums of Grisons
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info</p>	yellow	digiCULT xTree.public: The HTML view shows the creation date and, if different, the date of the last modification, which is usually identical to the creation date. The serialisations typically

		used in xTree.public are not accessible.
	red	museums.ch: The offers on museums.ch do not specify a creation or modification date.
	yellow	Valais museums: creation date of PDF is included. It appears that no subsequent modifications have been made.
	yellow	Museums of Grisons: creation date of PDF is included. It appears that no subsequent modifications have been made.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	digiCULT xTree.public: RDF XML via restricted access API
	green	museums.ch: see digiCULT xTree.public. Additionally, an XML download file is available.
	red	Valais museums: vocabulary exclusively available as PDF
	red	Museums of Grisons: vocabulary exclusively available as PDF
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	museums.ch, digiCULT xTree.public
	red	Valais museums, Museums of Grisons: no SKOS format available
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	red	Qualified mappings to other vocabularies are not available. There is also no corresponding mapping property in Wikidata.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	red	The licence is not specified in any of the available offers, neither on the website nor at concept level. It cannot be researched with reasonable effort in external offers either.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their	yellow	museums.ch and digiCULT xTree.public: Some limited metadata is available on the page https://www.museums.ch/de/fachwelt/fachthem/en/inventar-1159.html , but this website only

<p>provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>		provides basic information about the origin and maintenance of the vocabulary and the granularity of the concepts.
	yellow	Valais museums: The PDF version only provides limited vocabulary metadata in the introduction.
	red	Museums of Grisons: The PDF version contains little or no vocabulary metadata.
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>	yellow	<p>Concepts are not necessarily granular enough for modern museum documentation. Furthermore, homonyms are not distinguished as such. The structure of the hierarchy and the assignments of concepts and terms are not always easy to understand.</p>
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	yellow	<p>No definitions available. The categorisation of concepts in the classification tree helps to understand the concepts, but there is still plenty of room for interpretation.</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	yellow	<p>No definitions, no synonyms or alternative terms, no application examples. After all, there are language variants, and the organisation of concepts in the classification tree provides some guidance.</p>

3.26 UNESCO Thesaurus

<h3>3.26 UNESCO Thesaurus</h3>	
<p>Brief description</p>	<p>The UNESCO Thesaurus is a controlled vocabulary used for cataloguing and indexing documents and publications in the fields of education, culture, the natural sciences, the social sciences, communication, and information. It is continuously updated.</p> <p>Concepts are assigned to seven main subject areas, each of which is further differentiated hierarchically (Education; Science; Culture; Social and human sciences; Information and</p>

	communication; Politics, law and economics; Countries and country groupings).
Web link	https://vocabularies.unesco.org/thesaurus
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, geographical entities, periods/eras
Size (number of concepts)	4.494 (2025-11-24)
Languages	English, Arabic, Spanish, Russian, French
License	CC-BY-SA 3.0 IGO
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Editorial board: UNESCO Library and Documentation Service
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://vocabularies.unesco.org/documents/thesaurusintroeng.pdf
Community contributions possible?	Contributions and feedback via email: vocabularies@unesco.org
Interfaces / Data Transfer	SPARQL endpoint: https://vocabularies.unesco.org/sparql-form/ REST API: https://data.unesco.org/api/explore/v2.1/console Download files: https://vocabularies.unesco.org/exports/thesaurus/latest/
Mapping services	Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F40 NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F40
Available data formats / serialisations	PDF, RDF XML, JSON-LD, Turtle
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/40 FAIRsharing: 10.25504/FAIRsharing.81dc5f LOV: not available (2025-11-24) museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/unesco-thesaurus/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1218905

	Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2467479	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history	
Suitable for MDS elements	Classification , Place , Subject keyword	
Suitable for additional elements	Period/Style	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3)	green	

more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	green	Last modification date is specified, also in serialisations
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1)	green	

more info		
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	Structure according to ISO 25964
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	For many concepts, no definitions are available; their meaning has to be derived from the hierarchical context.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Only superordinate concepts and related concepts are provided. The vocabulary is available in several languages.

3.27 Virtual International Authority File (VIAF)

Brief description	<p>The Virtual International Authority File (VIAF) is a service that unites various authority files relating to individual persons, corporate bodies, works and geographical entities. Since 2012, it has been operated by the Online Computer Library Centre (OCLC) in collaboration with over 50 libraries and other institutions from 30 countries. VIAF was originally initiated by the German National Library (DNB) and the Library of Congress.</p> <p>Participating institutions regularly provide authority data,</p>
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	<p>which is collated, linked and grouped by VIAF. All descriptions of a particular entity are combined into a cluster, compiling the various names used for that entity. This service helps researchers to identify names, places, works and expressions while maintaining regional preferences in terms of language, spelling, and script.</p> <p>Each cluster provides direct links to the authority records incorporated into it. It also contains qualified links to other entities related to the cluster's subject, e.g., in the case of persons, to other persons, corporate bodies, works and places of publication.</p> <p>Both clusters and the source authority data are available via the API. Cluster records also contain structured basic information that can be used to correctly identify the entity, such as dates of birth and death for persons.</p>
Web link	https://viaf.org/en
Coverage of entities	persons, corporate bodies, works/objects, geographical entities (including buildings)
Size (number of concepts)	<p>No current information is available from the service provider.</p> <p>As of 2012, however, 25 million authority records, 110 million bibliographic data records, 20 million clusters, and 24 million relationships between authority records were already available.¹⁰</p>
Languages	Arabic, Chinese, Danish, English, Estonian, French, German, Greek, Hebrew, Italian, Japanese, Catalan, Korean, Croatian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Norwegian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovak, Spanish, Czech, Hungarian, Russian
License	ODC-By 1.0
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher and Editorial board: OCLC, supported by contributions from participating institutions
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://www.oclc.org/en/viaf.html
Community contributions possible?	<p>Interested institutions are required to undergo an application and admission process:</p> <p>https://www.oclc.org/de/viaf/contributing.html</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>https://www.oclc.org/developer/api/oclc-apis/viaf.en.html</p> <p>OpenAPI: https://developer.api.oclc.org/viaf-api (restricted access)</p> <p>Download of the complete data (last updated 2024-09-04):</p>

¹⁰ <https://www.semantic-web-journal.net/sites/default/files/swj294.pdf>

	https://viaf.org/de/viaf/data	
Mapping services	OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://refine.codefork.com/	
Available data formats / serialisations	XML, RDF XML, MARC21-XML; additionally via API: JSON, JSON-LD, UNIMARC-XML	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/2053 FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a15ac6 museumsvocabular.de: not available (2025-11-21) R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190620 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q54919	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science, science/technology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object title or name , Person/corporate body , Place , Institution providing record , Rights holder of media file , Repository of object	
Suitable for additional elements	Published Object Identifier , Related Work Set/Related Work/Object/ Object Identifier	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	Europeana	
Comments		
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in	green	

at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info		
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info	yellow	Creation date and modification information for the cluster only contained in XML format and not in the web display, nor in RDF XML, nor in MARC XML
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a	green	

community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info		
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	yellow	Licence information specified on the website for the overall offer, but not included in the serialisations.
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Information on cluster versioning is missing.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.28 Wikidata

Brief description	Wikidata is a free and open knowledge database. It stores structured data for Wikimedia projects, including Wikipedia, Wikivoyage, Wiktionary and Wikisource. Additionally, it allows entries that are independent of Wikimedia. Each piece of information in Wikidata consists of an item or entity ('Q' identifiers), properties ('P' identifiers), and statements. The content is available under a free licence and complies with the principles of Linked Open Data.
Web link	https://www.wikidata.org
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts, persons, corporate bodies, works/objects, geographical entities, periods/eras, buildings
Size (number of concepts)	119.383.718 (2025-11-19)
Languages	Indonesian, Malay, British English, German, English, Esperanto, Frisian, Luxembourgish, Dutch, Ripuarian, Scottish, Simple English, Sundanese, Turkish, Yoruba, Zazaki, Bosnian, Catalan, Danish, Estonian, Spanish, Basque, French, Galician, Interlingua, Italian, Kurdish, Latvian, Hungarian, Norwegian, Occitan, Polish, Portuguese, Brazilian Portuguese, Albanian, Finnish, Swedish, Toki Pona, Czech, Silesian, Greek, Belarusian, Bulgarian, Macedonian, Russian, Serbian, Ukrainian, Armenian, Yiddish, Hebrew, Arabic, Malay (Arabic script), Sindhi, Persian, Bengali, Tamil, Telugu, Malayalam, Pa'O, Georgian, Chinese, Chinese (Taiwan), Japanese, Cantonese, Min Nan, Korean. See also: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Multilingual
License	CC0 1.0 Universal
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Wikimedia Foundation Editorial responsibility: no institutional responsibility. Quality assurance is put into practice through a decentralised peer review process by members of the Wikimedia community.
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	Content: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Introduction Data model: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Data_model Further information: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:Contents

	<p>https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Glossary</p> <p>Notability criteria: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Notability/en-gb</p>
Community contributions possible?	<p>No conventional editorial team in the sense of institutional responsibility: Editorial tasks and revision of contributions are performed by members of the Wikimedia community who have defined roles, such as administrators. Options for participation: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Contribute</p> <p>Bots also make a significant contribution to data maintenance (see https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Bots).</p>
Interfaces / Data Transfer	<p>Documentation on OAI-PMH, SPARQL endpoint, REST API, MediaWiki Action API: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Data_access</p> <p>SPARQL endpoint: https://query.wikidata.org/sparql</p>
Mapping services	<p>OpenRefine Reconciliation API: https://wikidata.reconci.link/en/api</p> <p>Cocoda Mapping Tool: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/app/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1940</p> <p>https://coli-conc.gbv.de/services/wikidata/</p> <p>NFDI4Objects Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/nfdi4objects/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1940</p> <p>TS4NFDI Mapping Editor: https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/ts4nfdi/?fromScheme=http%3A%2F%2Fbartoc.org%2Fen%2Fnode%2F1940</p>
Available data formats / serialisations	XML, RDF XML, JSON, N-Triples, Turtle, Notation3
Reference in registries / Wikidata	<p>BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/1940</p> <p>FAIRsharing: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6s749p</p> <p>LOV: not available (2025-11-13)</p> <p>museumsvokabular.de: https://museumsvokabular.de/wikidata/</p> <p>R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q370382</p> <p>Wikidata:http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2013</p>
Suitable for field of specialisation	Suitable for use across disciplines, e.g., for archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art, medical history, natural history/natural science,

	science/technology	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Materials , Techniques , Measurements , Person/corporate body , Place , Subject keyword , Rights holder of media file , Repository of object , Institution providing record For the element Alternative text the Wikidata property https://www.wikidata.org/entity/P11265 is used to indicate alternative texts in the data element for media file descriptions (LIDO: Resource Description)	
Suitable for additional elements	Culture , Period/Style , Role Actor	
Nutzung für Datenanreicherung in Portalen (Stand 02.2025)	Europeana , Collections from Colonial Contexts , museum-digital	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assess-ment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>Concepts may be deleted under certain conditions if the notability criteria are not met: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Deletion_policy. By following these criteria, it can be assumed that the concepts will remain available for the longest possible time. In the case of duplicates, redirects are used to ensure the stability of URIs.</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>Some vocabularies provide properties that allow targeted mapping to Wikidata, for instance: https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1014 (AAT) https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P1256</p>

FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info		(Iconclass) https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Property:P227 (GND)
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info	green	
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	yellow	Given the lack of a central editorial team, this is highly dependent on the content quality of entries. Definitions do not necessarily have to be included when creating entries.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	The quality of the entries can vary significantly. Some entries contain numerous statements, others contain only a few.

3.29 World Historical Gazetteer

Brief description	<p>The World Historical Gazetteer (WHG) is an online platform that links information about historical places across time, space and language barriers. Its aim is to promote a deeper understanding of spatial history and improve the discoverability of places that have had multiple names over time. As place names and characteristics change significantly due to historical dynamics, the development of interlinked, diverse and multilingual place directories is crucial.</p> <p>The WHG provides tools and services for using and disseminating stable, linkable temporal-spatial geographic data. Based on this infrastructure, researchers can contribute historical place names and data from various sources, time periods and cultural and linguistic contexts. The project aims to create a resource for structured, reusable, and linked information about places.</p> <p>A database of 13 million geographical features forms the starting point, bringing together information from GeoNames, Wikidata, VIAF, TGN, and other sources. When new datasets contributed by researchers are integrated, they are matched, enriched, and published in the WHG Union Index. Individual datasets can be referenced as publications. PeriodO can be used as a temporal filter.</p> <p>So far, the WHG has primarily been used in the context of digital humanities for research projects in that field.</p>
Web link	https://whgazetteer.org/ (v.3.0 beta, 2025-11-27)
Coverage of entities	geographical entities
Size (number of concepts)	13 million (2025-11-26)
Languages	English, place name variants in various languages
License	<p>CC BY-NC 4.0. For individual research datasets diverging licences may apply.</p> <p>External vocabularies (e.g. Geonames, Wikidata, VIAF, Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN), Viabundus) are available under their respective licences.</p>
Publisher / Editorial responsibility	<p>University of Pittsburgh Institute for Spatial History Innovation (since 2025)</p> <p>University of Pittsburgh World History Center (2017-2025)</p>
Editorial team active?	Yes
Web link documentation	https://docs.whgazetteer.org/
Community contributions	Upload of own datasets, enrichment of existing data:

possible?	https://docs.whgazetteer.org/content/guides/uploading.html , https://whgazetteer.org/workbench/ Comment feature ('Add note') for correction suggestions	
Interfaces / Data Transfer	OpenAPI (Swagger): https://whgazetteer.org/api/schema/swagger-ui/ Downloads are offered for a number of research datasets (91 available, 2025-11-27). In addition, it is also possible to download parts of the holdings on a record-by-record basis. Registration is required to access the download function.	
Mapping services	WHG Reconciliation Service: https://www.w3.org/community/reports/reconciliation/CG-FINAL-specs-0.2-20230410/ , https://docs.whgazetteer.org/content/technical/apis.html#reconciliation-service-api	
Available data formats / serialisations	Linked Places format (LPF) : GeoJSON Extension with the option of time-based attributes LP-TSV (Linked Places Tab-Separated Values) for core data elements	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: https://bartoc.org/en/node/20423 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-30) LOV: not available (2025-11-30) museums vokabular.de: not available (2025-11-27) R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1753258 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q130424771	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, architectural history, ethnology, history, cultural history, art history	
Suitable for MDS elements	Place , Subject keyword (place as subject)	
Suitable for additional elements	Repository/Location (former location)	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	-	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a	yellow	It is not possible to address the vocabulary

globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info		directly with a unique identifier. However, it can be addressed indirectly via either Wikidata or registry entries.
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	

<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>Publication date/last modification date included in LPF format of research datasets, no display of this information on the website</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>LPF is a JSON-LD extension.</p>
<p>At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>The links to the extensively mapped sources are included in LPF format; they are not displayed on the website.</p>
<p>The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	<p>In the LPF format of the research datasets, free-text reference to the standard licence CC-BY-NC 4.0 and, if applicable, any deviating licence provisions of data providers.</p>
<p>Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>green</p>	
<p>The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3)</p>	<p>green</p>	

more info		
Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info	green	By providing coordinates, it is possible to locate the places.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info	green	

3.30 Wordnet Culture [*Wortnetz Kultur, WNK*]

Brief description	<p>Wordnet Culture (Wortnetz Kultur) is a hierarchically structured thesaurus for indexing generic concepts from the fields of cultural anthropology, archaeology, art history, and cultural history. It was developed to standardise the data used by the cultural services of the Landschaftsverband Rheinland and to make it interoperable.</p> <p>Structurally modelled on the AAT, it provides a vocabulary covering actors, activities, events, brand names, materials, objects, physical characteristics, time periods, cultures and styles, as well as additional abstract concepts.</p> <p>Each concept should include a definition, alternative names and an English translation of the preferred term (the latter currently under development).</p>
Web link	<p>https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/</p> <p>http://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http%3A//lvr.vocnet.org/wnk/&startNode=wk000249</p>
Coverage of entities	Generic concepts for objects/works
Size (number of concepts)	8.684 (RDF dump 2025-11-26)
Languages	German, preferred terms also in English
License	CC BY 4.0

Publisher / Editorial responsibility	Publisher: Landschaftsverband Rheinland (LVR) Editorial board: Long-term secure, continuously working team, part of the 'Digital Cultural Heritage' department of the Landschaftsverband Rheinland	
Editorial team active?	Yes	
Web link documentation	https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/about https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/team	
Community contributions possible?	Ongoing, based on the needs of the LVR collections and projects; users' requests and comments can also be sent to the editorial team by email.	
Interfaces / Data Transfer	Data download (https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/about); interface: REST API (restricted access)	
Mapping services	-	
Available data formats / serialisations	JSON-LD, RDF XML, Turtle, N-Triples, TriG, JSON	
Reference in registries / Wikidata	BARTOC: http://bartoc.org/en/node/17786 FAIRsharing: not available (2025-11-30) LOV: not available (2025-11-30) museumsvocabular.de: https://museumsvocabular.de/wortnetz-kultur-wnk/ R:hovono: https://vokabulare.geschichte.uni-halle.de/vokabular.php?uri=Q1190596 Wikidata: http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q136665478	
Suitable for field of specialisation	Archaeology, ethnology, history, cultural history, art	
Suitable for MDS elements	Object type or designation , Classification , Materials , Techniques , Subject keyword (type of object as a subject)	
Suitable for additional elements	Period/Style	
Use for data enrichment in portals (status 10/2025)	No	
Comments	-	
FAIRness		
	Assessment	Explanation
The vocabulary is assigned a	green	

globally unique and persistent identifier (PID). (F.1) more info		
Constituent concepts of the vocabulary are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers (PID). (F.1) more info	green	
It is possible to search for a vocabulary or concept and output a corresponding web identifier. (F.4) (more info)	green	
The vocabulary is available in at least one repository that is recognised by the community. (R.1.3) more info	green	
When the vocabulary or concept identifier is dereferenced, a machine-readable or human-readable representation is returned, as required. (F.4) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are registered or indexed in a searchable engine or a resource. (F.3) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts can be accessed via a standardised communication protocol. Ideally, this would be an open, free and universally applicable protocol that enables authentication and authorisation where applicable. (A.1, A.1.1, A.1.2) more info	green	
Vocabulary and constituent concepts are persistent over time. (A.2) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts are	green	Date of last modification is displayed and is also included in the data serialisations. The creation

appropriately versioned. (A.2) more info		date is only displayed in digiCULT xTree.public.
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use a formal, accessible and broadly applicable, and preferably machine-understandable language for knowledge representation (RDF XML with SKOS or OWL, JSON-LD). (I.1) more info	green	
At least one of the representations conforms to a community standard for vocabularies. (R.1) more info	green	
The vocabulary and constituent concepts use qualified references (mappings) to other vocabularies, which are themselves as FAIR-compliant as possible. (I.3, I.2) more info	green	Yes, mappings to AAT, GND, Wikidata and other vocabularies are available.
The vocabulary is released with a clear and accessible data usage licence, which is preferably machine-readable. (R.1.1) more info	green	
Sufficient metadata is provided for the vocabulary and constituent concepts, including information on their provenance and maintenance. (F.2, R.1) more info	yellow	Free-text overview documentation is available explaining the priorities in the development of the concepts. However, this should be supplemented with information on the coverage of the vocabulary and the publication strategy for concepts that have not yet been finalised (status 'in progress'). Non-finalised concepts that are currently being edited are also published. The editing status is displayed on the website and is included in serialisations.
The vocabulary complies with relevant community standards. It contains essential concepts and terms for a specific field, reflects knowledge about that domain, and can be used with existing	green	

<p>data standards and data models. (R.1, R.1.2, R.1.3) more info</p>		
<p>Definitions are sufficient to help users understand the meaning of each concept. (R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>Compared to the stated objective (Wie arbeiten wir?), the concepts have been developed to varying degrees of completeness. Definitions are available for 53% of the concepts (based on the RDF dump, 2025-11-26). However, the contextual meaning is also clarified by the hierarchical classification of the concepts.</p>
<p>The vocabulary and constituent concepts are described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes. This includes terms, synonyms, definitions, examples of use and cross-references to support the interpretation and reuse of concepts. (F.2, R.1) more info</p>	<p>yellow</p>	<p>The level of detail in the concept data records varies greatly. There are detailed entries with long definitions, one or more designations, explanations, related concepts and references to equivalents in other vocabularies. An example is: https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/wnk/wk007511. In contrast, here is an example of a brief entry: https://wnk-viewer.lvr.de/wnk/wk002586</p>

4. Literature

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5. Change log

v1.0.1 (2026-02-09)

- Title page: Addition of publication metadata
- Section 3.1-3.30, category “Suitable for MDS elements”: Addition of the element “Rights holder of media file” to GND, ULAN, VIAF
- Abstract, section 3.1-3.30, category “Suitable for MDS elements”: Update of links to the *Minimum Record Recommendation for Museums and Collections* in the Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek wiki
- Spelling, punctuation and formatting corrections